

Review

Biopolymeric micro and nanoscale colloidal delivery systems for controlled drug release in pharmaceutical sector

Razvan Odocheanu^{a,b}, Lavinia-Florina Calinoiu^{a,b}, Gheorghe-Adrian Martau^{a,b},
Dan Cristian Vodnar^{a,b,*}

^a Faculty of Food Science and Technology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, Calea Mănăştur 3-5, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

^b Institute of Life Sciences, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, Calea Mănăştur 3-5, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

HIGHLIGHTS

- Biopolymer systems improve controlled drug release and therapeutic outcomes.
- Stimuli-responsive biopolymers enable precision medicine.
- Diffusion, swelling, osmosis, and erosion define mass transport mechanisms.
- Scale-up and *in vivo* validation remain key barriers to translation.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Controlled release
Biopolymers
Target release
Biocompatibility
Targeted therapy
Biodegradability

ABSTRACT

Controlled release delivery systems have become a focal point in the pharmaceutical sector, with biopolymers playing a crucial role in enabling precise modulation of active compound release. Polymers, categorized into natural and synthetic types, are widely used due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and versatility. Natural biopolymers, such as proteins, polysaccharides, and microbial polyesters, offer high bioactivity but may encounter challenges related to mechanical strength and degradation rates. Synthetic polymers, including poly (lactic acid) and polycaprolactone, are engineered to provide enhanced stability and tunable release profiles. Integrating these biopolymers in controlled release systems enhances targeted therapeutic outcomes by ensuring sustained drug release in pharmaceutical applications, thereby improving drug efficacy and minimising side effects. This review demonstrates that utilizing novel approaches involving biopolymeric materials for controlled-release delivery systems is a promising route for precise control, offering important industrial potential. Integrating these materials in the pharmaceutical industry represents a breakthrough in enhancing release profiles and targeting specific applications (e.g. cancer therapy, drug delivery, nutraceutical delivery). The latest advancements in biopolymeric materials and their applications in controlled release systems, focusing on targeted release strategies, are comprehensively discussed. Key release mechanisms (diffusion, erosion, and swelling) are also critically compared for targeted applications. Despite progress, challenges like scalability and

* Corresponding author at: Faculty of Food Science and Technology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, Calea Mănăştur 3-5, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania.

E-mail address: dan.vodnar@usamvcluj.ro (D.C. Vodnar).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2026.134626>

Received 18 December 2025; Received in revised form 25 March 2026; Accepted 12 April 2026

Available online 13 April 2026

0960-8524/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

in vivo validation require further research to bridge lab-scale innovations to commercial applications. Biopolymeric delivery systems enable controllable release kinetics through material-structure interactions, supporting rational design of targeted pharmaceutical formulations with translational relevance.

1. Introduction

The evolution of controlled biocargo delivery has advanced from early macroscopic, implantable, and depot-based systems developed during the 1960 s–1990 s to biodegradable polymeric depots and, more recently, to highly engineered micro- and nanoscale delivery platforms capable of achieving targeted, stimuli-responsive, and temporally regulated release profiles (H. Park et al., 2022). Conventional formulations still suffer from pervasive limitations, notably initial burst release, suboptimal bioavailability, off-target toxicity, rapid enzymatic degradation of labile therapeutics, and poorly controlled pharmacokinetics, which motivate the shift toward engineered delivery vehicles (Adepu & Ramakrishna, 2021). Advanced delivery platforms occupy a pivotal position at the convergence of pharmaceutical innovation, addressing and overcoming fundamental limitations. These challenges have led to intensive research into biopolymer-based matrices that enable controlled, sustained, and stimuli-responsive release of active compounds. Polymers are macromolecules built from repeated monomeric units (e.g., nucleotides, amino acids, monosaccharides) and include classes such as polyesters, polyhydroxyalkanoates, and lignin derivatives (Ghosh et al., 2021). They are broadly classified as natural (biopolymers, proteins, polysaccharides, polynucleotides, and some microbial polyesters) and synthetic polymers, each offering distinct functional attributes (Reddy et al., 2021). Synthetic polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and Polyethylene glycol (PEG) provide enhanced tunability, mechanical robustness, and controlled biodegradation, whereas natural biopolymers afford superior biocompatibility and biofunctionality but often suffer from variability in degradation and mechanical properties (Mtibe et al., 2021). Hybrid formulations that combine natural and synthetic components are therefore increasingly used to reconcile bioactivity with structural performance; nonetheless, challenges such as poor drug solubility and limited bioavailability for labile therapeutics (e.g., siRNA) necessitate bespoke biopolymer design and formulation strategies (Zargar et al., 2019). Precedence Research reports that the global biopolymer sector reached a valuation of USD 19.4 billion in 2024, with forecasts projecting an expansion to USD 52.3 billion by 2034. This robust growth trajectory reflects escalating environmental and health-sustainability approaches, supportive regulatory frameworks, and the intrinsic biocompatibility of biopolymeric materials in therapeutic contexts. Production infrastructure has responded accordingly, raising the biopolymer production from 2.1 million tonnes in 2023 to 2.4 million tonnes in 2024, with projections indicating a rise to 5.7 million tonnes by 2029 (Bidwai, 2025). Despite these gains, biopolymers retain a 2–3 × cost premium over conventional petrochemical polymers, trading at USD 2–6/kg comparing to USD 1–2/kg. PLA exemplifies this range, commanding USD 2–3/kg, while polypropylene averages USD 1/kg in North America and USD 1.5/kg in Europe (Business, 2026).

Several challenges persist in current drug delivery systems, particularly in ensuring precise, targeted, and controlled release. The physicochemical properties of delivery carriers, including particle size, significantly influence their absorption, bioavailability, and *in vivo* stability. While larger carriers exhibit poor solubility and limited cellular uptake, smaller counterparts often present challenges related to structural integrity and controlled drug release. Furthermore, optimizing biopolymer characteristics, including surface charge, hydrophilicity, and degradation kinetics, is crucial for improving drug transport and bioavailability. Although advanced approaches, such as nanotechnology-based modifications and functionalised biopolymer matrices, show promise in overcoming these limitations, extensive *in*

vivo studies are required to validate their translational potential and clinical efficacy (Ezike et al., 2023). Delivery systems, in general, utilise inorganic materials, polymers, biopolymers or hybrid formulations to develop advanced drug carriers, including vesicles, micelles, nanocapsules, nanospheres, microspheres, microemulsions, films, and hydrogels (Alshawwa et al., 2022). Various mechanisms govern drug release from the biopolymeric carriers, such as diffusion, polymer degradation, matrix swelling, and affinity-based interactions (Puiggali-Jou et al., 2019). A fundamental objective of controlled drug delivery is maintaining drug concentrations within an optimal therapeutic range, enhancing efficacy while minimising systemic side effects.

The aim of this review is to provide a comprehensive and critical analysis of the design, development, and functional optimization of biopolymer-based controlled release systems, with an emphasis on their role in modulating the release kinetics of active compounds in pharmaceutical applications. By examining the interplay between biopolymer composition, structural characteristics, and physicochemical properties, this review seeks to elucidate how these factors influence the performance, stability, and efficacy of controlled release formulations. By integrating current knowledge from materials science, biotechnology, and formulation engineering, this review aims to identify and critically assess the state-of-the-art advances in biopolymer design, including surface modifications, hybrid composites, and nanostructuring approaches, with the goal of achieving precise targeting and controlled release profiles.

2. Fundamentals of controlled release mechanisms for biopolymers

2.1. Release mechanisms

In temporally controlled delivery systems, various mechanisms regulate the kinetics of drug release over an extended period (Fig. 1). Key factors influencing this modulation include the administration route (such as parenteral, oral, or local), the physicochemical properties of the drug (e.g., small molecules or macromolecules, hydrophobic or hydrophilic), and the release profiles of the drug (whether sustained, constant, or pulsatile release). These elements are crucial in determining the overall release dynamics (Shuying Wang et al., 2020). In the context of controlled release for pharmaceutical applications, four common release mechanisms are employed: diffusion-controlled release, where the substance is gradually transported through the matrix; swelling-controlled release, which relies on the expansion of the material to release the active compound; erosion-controlled release, where the matrix degrades over time, releasing the substance as it breaks down and osmosis, where the delivery is made through osmotic pumps (Wang et al., 2022). The release mechanisms described provide a mechanistic basis for the rational design of biopolymeric micro- and nanoscale delivery systems discussed in subsequent sections. Diffusion- and swelling-controlled release are primarily governed by polymer permeability, hydrophilicity, and crosslinking density, whereas erosion- and biodegradation-driven systems depend on backbone chemistry, crystallinity, and degradation pathways to achieve sustained release. Osmotically controlled platforms enable near-zero-order release through membrane-regulated water influx, while ion-exchange and prodrug strategies exploit electrostatic interactions and site-specific bioconversion to further tailor release kinetics. Together, these mechanisms directly inform material selection, formulation strategies, and architectural design choices across diverse biopolymeric delivery platforms. For example, hydrophilic polysaccharides such as chitosan and

alginate are commonly used in swelling-controlled oral or mucosal delivery systems, where crosslinking density and ionic interactions regulate solvent uptake and drug diffusion (Huang et al., 2017). In contrast, biodegradable polyesters such as poly(lactic acid) and poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) are widely used in erosion-controlled injectable formulations, in which sustained release is governed by backbone hydrolysis and bulk erosion kinetics (Burkersroda et al., 2002).

2.2. Diffusion mechanism

The principle of diffusion is based on the movement of solute driven by concentration gradients between regions. Drug diffusion can be quantitatively described using Fick's law. However, it is essential to note that Fick's law only applies to simple, well-defined delivery systems where time, space, and concentration gradients are independent of the diffusivity. Diffusion-controlled drug delivery systems are generally classified into two primary categories: reservoir systems and matrix systems (Fu & Kao, 2010).

A reservoir system typically consists of an active layer and a barrier layer, with the active ingredient housed within the active layer. In such systems, the diffusion rate of the active ingredient is influenced by the properties of the barrier layer, such as its thickness, surface area, and permeability (Stevenson et al., 2012). The release of active ingredients generally involves three sequential processes: solvent diffusion, dissolution of the active ingredient, and its subsequent diffusion. In cases where the boundary layer resistance is negligible, the release rate is predominantly determined by the diffusion of the active ingredient. When the active ingredient is sufficiently present in the packaging material, diffusion typically follows zero-order kinetics, wherein the active ingredient is released at a constant rate, thus achieving the intended controlled release (Urbaniak et al., 2024).

These active ingredients are uniformly distributed throughout a non-biodegradable and non-erodible matrix in a matrix system. The release rate is governed by the system's geometric configuration, the matrix material's characteristics, and the active ingredient's properties. The release process in a matrix system involves several steps: dissolution of the active ingredient within the matrix, diffusion of the active ingredient through the matrix, and detachment from the matrix surface. The active

ingredient diffusion through the matrix typically serves as the rate-limiting step. Without a barrier layer, the matrix system typically exhibits a burst release in the initial phase, followed by a gradual decline in the release rate over time. There are several matrix systems: (i) the drug is either dissolved or dispersed within the matrix and diffuses via the solution-diffusion mechanism; (ii) the drug is dispersed throughout the matrix and diffuses through channels and pores within the structure (Wang et al., 2022).

2.2.1. Swelling mechanism

Swelling-controlled drug delivery systems represent a class of devices in which the entrapped bioactive compound remains immobilized within a highly entangled matrix, preventing diffusion under normal conditions. Upon contact with an aqueous environment, water molecules diffuse into the system, triggering a series of changes in the matrix that enable the release of the bioactive compound (Siepmann & Siepmann, 2011). This process is fundamentally driven by the swelling of the polymer matrix, which increases its volume and facilitates the release of the drug. The swelling mechanism can be described through three sequential steps: water diffusion into the matrix, polymer chain relaxation, and the subsequent dissolution and diffusion of the active ingredient. In swelling-controlled release systems, the polymer matrix undergoes significant morphological changes upon exposure to specific solvents, typically water (S. Wang et al., 2020). The matrix absorbs the solvent molecules, causing it to swell and expand. This swelling increases the interstitial spaces between the polymer molecules, creating channels that release the bioactive compound. A key feature of this system is the glass transition of the polymer material when it absorbs solvent, which alters its structure and facilitates the dissolution of the entrapped active ingredient. As a result, the diffusion coefficient of the bioactive compound increases, enabling it to diffuse through the polymer matrix and be released into the surrounding environment. One of the distinguishing aspects of swelling-controlled systems is that the matrix does not undergo degradation or erosion, thus maintaining its original shape throughout the release process. The swelling-induced release of bioactive compounds proceeds in multiple stages: solvent absorption, volume expansion, active ingredient dissolution, and diffusion (Adrover et al., 2021).

Fig. 1. Controlled release mechanisms in bio-polymeric delivery systems. (Created with Biorender).

2.2.2. Erosion and biodegradation mechanisms

The drug is distributed within a biodegradable matrix, similar to the matrix system in the biodegradation mechanism. The primary distinction between the two is that while the volume of the matrix system remains constant throughout the release period, the biodegradable system interacts with the surrounding environment. It degrades simultaneously with the release of the drug (Visan et al., 2021). Controlled drug release in biodegradable systems typically involves three degradation mechanisms: i) physical processes, such as abrasion, fracture, or disintegration; ii) chemical processes, including dissolution, ionisation, or protonation; and iii) biological processes, such as pH changes, enzymatic activity, or immune responses. In polymeric systems, controlled degradation is governed by specific mechanisms, including backbone cleavage, side-chain degradation, crosslink cleavage, and chain transfer processes (Hartman et al., 2020).

In bioactive compound delivery systems, the erosion mechanism is critical in controlling the release kinetics, particularly in biodegradable polymer-based devices. Bulk erosion is a typical degradation process in which mass loss occurs throughout the material as the polymer hydrates. Water penetrates the polymer at a rate faster than its degradation, initiating a reduction in molecular weight and a loss of mechanical properties from the onset of degradation. In contrast, the mass loss itself is delayed. The polymer's external dimensions remain unchanged until a critical point when disintegration occurs (Hynes et al., 2023).

Most biodegradable polymers currently available degrade *via* bulk erosion, which typically involves simple hydrolysis of the primary chain bonds. Achieving surface erosion, where degradation occurs primarily at the material surface, is challenging, and most systems degrade through bulk erosion. The ideal erosion-controlled system for bioactive compound delivery would be one where surface erosion exclusively governs the release of the bioactive compound, ensuring that the release rate is proportional to the device surface area. This is particularly advantageous in maintaining a consistent release profile, as surface erosion-controlled drug release can achieve zero-order kinetics when the surface area remains constant (Silva et al., 2023).

2.2.3. Osmosis mechanism

The distinctive feature of osmotically-controlled release systems is their ability to maintain a constant release rate of the bioactive compound over an extended period, facilitated by the steady osmotic pressure differential across the semi-permeable membrane. Osmotic pumps typically comprise osmotic agents, bioactive compounds, and solvents. Upon exposure to an aqueous environment, water diffuses into the system to balance the osmotic pressure differential across the semi-permeable membrane (S. Wang et al., 2020). This influx of water displaces the dissolved bioactive compound, which is then released through precisely controlled aqueous orifices in the membrane. These orifices are typically formed by incorporating water-soluble materials into the membrane that dissolve upon contact with water. Single-compartment osmotic pumps are often employed for water-soluble bioactive compounds. Multilayer osmotic pumps are preferred for bioactive compounds that are insoluble in water. These systems typically feature a rigid outer membrane and a flexible inner membrane, designed to accommodate the release of the bioactive compound (Lautenschläger et al., 2014).

2.2.4. Ion exchange and prodrug systems

Ion exchange resins (IER) are insoluble polymers featuring either acidic or basic functional groups, which enable them to exchange counter-ions in aqueous solutions. Depending on the nature of the exchangeable ion, IERs are classified into cationic or anionic exchange resins based on whether they exchange cations or anions. The effectiveness of ion exchange resins in controlled drug delivery systems is primarily influenced by their physical properties, such as the degree of cross-linking, porosity, acid-base strength, stability, purity, and particle size. One notable application of ion exchange resins is drug-controlled release, mainly by forming drug-resin complexes (resinate) (Srikanth

et al., 2010). Ion exchange is a promising strategy for the controlled release of charged solutes, including ionised small molecule drugs and larger biomolecules like DNAs and RNAs. The charged polymers in IERs bind electrostatically to oppositely charged drug molecules, facilitating their release. *In vivo*, naturally occurring ions (e.g., Cl, Na) can gradually replace the bound drug, leading to a slow, sustained release of the bioactive compound (Guo et al., 2009). Additionally, the layer-by-layer assembly technique offers a means to enhance drug loading within IERs by forming multiple layers, which increases the drug loading capacity and helps achieve the desired therapeutic efficacy. This approach makes ion exchange resins an effective and viable option for the prolonged and controlled release of various bioactive compounds, thereby improving their therapeutic outcomes (Borodkin, 2023).

A prodrug is an inactive form of a bioactive compound designed to be activated through spontaneous processes, such as hydrolytic degradation, or *via* bio-catalytic mechanisms at or near its pharmacological target. This design enables the selective release of the active bioactive compound at its target site, enhancing therapeutic efficacy while minimising side effects. Prodrugs are commonly employed to optimise the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of bioactive compounds, ensuring that the therapeutic agent is released precisely at the site of action (Delahousse et al., 2019). The design of prodrugs typically involves three key components: (a) the active moiety, which is responsible for the bioactive compound's therapeutic activity; (b) a cleavable labile chemical moiety, also known as the linker, which is conjugated to the active moiety through functional groups such as hydroxyl, carboxylic, amine, carbonyl, or phosphate groups; and (c) a targeting moiety, which ensures the specific delivery of the prodrug to the target site, such as affected cells or tissues. The targeting moiety often includes polypeptides or monoclonal antibodies (mAb) that bind specifically to markers or receptors overexpressed in the affected tissue (Singh et al., 2008).

Two major principles guide the design of prodrugs: (i) the structural characteristics of the active moiety, where the targeting moiety masks the pharmacodynamic activity of the bioactive compound until it reaches the desired site, and (ii) the bioconversion mechanism, which governs how the linker will degrade. This degradation can occur either gradually or immediately, enabling the controlled release of the bioactive compound once the pro-drug reaches its intended target (Rautio et al., 2018).

2.3. Factors affecting release kinetics

In addition to material- and drug-specific parameters, quantitative interpretation of release behavior from biopolymeric systems commonly relies on mathematical release kinetic models, which are essential tools in pharmaceutical formulation design. These models enable comparisons between formulations, the identification of dominant release mechanisms, and the rational optimization of carrier properties (Khalbas et al., 2024). Diffusion-controlled systems are frequently described using the Higuchi model, which assumes Fickian diffusion from a homogeneous matrix and predicts a square-root-of-time dependence of cumulative release; this model is particularly applicable to low-solubility bioactive compounds dispersed in non-eroding or slowly eroding polymer matrices (Mohsin et al., 2025). However, its applicability is limited when significant polymer swelling, erosion, or geometry changes occur. To address more complex transport phenomena, the Korsmeyer–Peppas semi-empirical model is widely used, particularly for polymeric matrices and particulate systems during early release stages (Heredia et al., 2022). The release exponent derived from this model provides mechanistic insight into whether transport is governed primarily by Fickian diffusion, anomalous (non-Fickian) behavior, or case II transport associated with polymer relaxation and swelling. Zero-order and first-order kinetic models are also routinely applied to describe systems exhibiting constant release rates or concentration-dependent release, respectively, with zero-order kinetics being particularly

desirable for maintaining therapeutic drug levels but challenging to achieve in matrix-based systems without specific architectural design. In biodegradable polymeric carriers, erosion-controlled release is often described using surface-erosion models such as the Hopfenberg model, while empirical models such as the Weibull function are used to flexibly fit complex release profiles when multiple mechanisms operate simultaneously. Importantly, the selection and interpretation of kinetic models must be aligned with polymer properties, particle geometry, and degradation behavior, as variations in molecular weight, crosslink density, hydrophilicity, and crystallinity directly influence fitted model parameters. Consequently, release modeling should not be treated solely as a curve-fitting exercise but as a mechanistic framework that links drug-related and polymer-related factors to observed release profiles, supporting rational formulation development and comparative assessment of biopolymeric delivery systems (Unagolla & Jayasuriya, 2018).

2.3.1. Drug-related factors

Several factors significantly influence the release and bioavailability of bioactive compounds in controlled-release drug delivery systems, including the bioactive compound's dose, molecular size, and solubility. These factors interact with the physicochemical properties of the matrix and the dynamic processes occurring within the dosage form, such as swelling, diffusion, and erosion, to determine the drug release kinetics (Varma et al., 2004). The bioactive compound dose plays a critical role in its release rate; for example, increasing the curcumin concentration within PLGA (poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid)) nanoparticles elevates the diffusion gradient, leading to faster initial release followed by sustained release due to polymer erosion (Sun et al., 2024). Increasing the bioactive compound within a matrix leads to a higher concentration gradient at the diffusion front, accelerating the release rate. However, this increased concentration does not always translate into an effective release for poorly soluble bioactive compounds. For instance, bioactive compounds with low solubility (hydrochlorothiazide, taxol, furosemide, dabrafenib mesylate) often face incomplete release due to their limited solubility and dissolution rate in the matrix (Fink et al., 2020). In such cases, the bioactive compound may remain undissolved within the matrix, impairing the system's ability to deliver the compound effectively. Molecular size is another crucial factor influencing the diffusivity of bioactive compounds within the matrix. Larger molecules typically exhibit reduced diffusivity because they are more constrained by polymer structure, particularly when the matrix has a dense network of polymer chains. This can hinder the bioactive compound movement through the gel layer and thus slow its release. Specifically, bioactive compounds with higher molecular weights are often poorly diffusible in hydrophilic matrices due to the resistance imposed by the polymer's aqueous gel structure. This limitation becomes more significant in matrix systems designed for controlled release, as the gel structure regulates the transport of the drug, preventing larger molecules from diffusing efficiently (Fink et al., 2020). However, the chitosan/insulin polyelectrolyte complex demonstrates high stability and a strong interaction between insulin and chitosan, resulting in more consistent diffusion, especially at low and moderate chitosan/insulin ratios, compared to hydrophobic systems (Robles et al., 2014). Solubility is perhaps the most influential factor in the release of bioactive compounds. The solubility of a bioactive compound in the surrounding medium determines the rate at which it can diffuse from the matrix into the bloodstream. Highly soluble compounds generally exhibit faster release as they dissolve quickly and readily diffuse through the gel layer.

In contrast, due to their slow dissolution rate, sparingly soluble bioactive compounds face challenges in achieving complete release. This dissolution rate is critical in determining the speed and extent of drug release, especially in matrix systems where the gel layer must undergo hydration and swelling for the bioactive compound to be transported. For poorly soluble bioactive compounds, the system may rely on additional mechanisms, such as surfactants, carrier systems, or drug-cyclodextrin inclusion complexes, to improve solubility and facilitate

drug release (Ward et al., 2020).

2.3.2. Polymer-related factors

Polymer-related factors are pivotal in defining the characteristics and performance of controlled-release delivery systems for bioactive compounds. The choice of polymer directly influences the diffusional and mechanical properties of the gel layer and bioactive compound-depleted regions, thereby affecting the release profile. Polymers with sufficient polarity can interact effectively with the aqueous medium, generating energy that facilitates the dispersion of polymer chains from their glassy state, promoting the formation of a gel layer. High-viscosity polymers generally exhibit rapid hydration and form stable gel structures, contributing to the controlled release of the bioactive compound. This property can mitigate the burst release effect and extend the release period.

In contrast, polymers with slower hydration rates may lead to a higher initial release, which may not be desirable in particular applications (Venkatesh et al., 2022). Polymer particle properties, including size and distribution, further modulate the performance of controlled-release delivery systems. The size of polymer particles plays a critical role in the rate of hydration and release of the bioactive compound. For instance, larger particles of hydroxyl-propyl methylcellulose (HPMC) hydrate more slowly, resulting in less efficient sustained release, whereas smaller particles tend to facilitate more controlled release. Research indicates that larger HPMC particles in formulations with lower polymer content can lead to burst release effects, as the polymer network may be insufficient to regulate the release (Kamaly et al., 2016). Viscosity, a crucial factor influenced by polymer type and particle size, plays a significant role in matrix formation. Polymers with higher viscosity contribute to forming thicker gel layers, which can impede diffusion, thereby slowing the release rate. This effect is especially evident when the polymer content increases as the gel layer becomes denser, creating a more significant barrier to water penetration and diffusion of the bioactive compound. On the other hand, polymers with lower viscosity or those that form less dense gels may facilitate faster release due to increased water penetration and compound diffusion (Fu et al., 2008).

3. Types of biopolymers used in controlled release delivery systems

Polysaccharide-based, protein-based, lipid-based, and synthetic biopolymer drug delivery systems possess unique characteristics that influence their application in pharmaceutical formulations. Polysaccharides like chitosan and alginate are widely used due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low cost. However, their drug encapsulation capacity is often limited, and factors like pH and enzymatic degradation can affect their release profiles (Behrooznia & Nourmohammadi, 2024). Also, protein-based systems are effective for the targeted delivery of biologics, offering high drug-binding affinity and specificity. Nevertheless, their stability is compromised by enzymatic degradation and conformational changes under physiological conditions, necessitating modification strategies to enhance their robustness (Hong et al., 2020). Lipid-based systems, such as liposomes and solid lipid nanoparticles, provide superior drug solubility, high encapsulation efficiency, and controlled release capabilities for hydrophobic compounds (Mall et al., 2024). However, they are prone to instability issues such as oxidation and hydrolysis, leading to reduced shelf-life and potential loss of drug activity (Sezer et al., 2014). Synthetic polymers like PLA and PCL offer controlled biodegradability and tunable physicochemical properties, allowing for precise manipulation of release rates and high biocompatibility (Homaieghar & Boccaccini, 2022; Srivastava et al., 2024). Despite these advantages, their complex synthesis routes and higher production costs can limit their widespread use (Jem & Tan, 2020). Each system's selection must be aligned with the therapeutic requirements of the drug, including the desired release

profile, stability, and production scalability.

3.1. Polysaccharide-based biopolymer systems

3.1.1. Alginate-based systems

Alginate is an anionic polysaccharide composed of β -D-mannuronic

Table 1

Comprehensive overview of polysaccharide-based biopolymer systems for controlled release and targeted therapeutic effects in the pharmaceutical sector.

Bioactive compound/drug	Biopolymer used	Target destination/area	Release mechanism	Results obtained	Ref.
<i>Androctonus australis hector</i> (Aah) venom and its toxic fraction	Calcium-Alginate nanoparticles	Lymphatic organs such as the spleen and the lymph nodes	Swelling	The immune protection was confirmed by the histological analysis of key organs affected during scorpion envenomation, such as the heart, lungs, and liver.	(Nait Mohamed & Laraba-Djebari, 2016)
HbsAg and CpG motifs (hepatitis B antigen)	Alginate-coated chitosan nanoparticle	Gut-associated lymphoid tissue, specifically the Peyer's patches in the intestine	Diffusion	Immunization studies demonstrated that the nanoparticle-based formulations enhanced immune responses.	(Borges et al., 2007)
Recombinant hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg)	Alginate-coated chitosan nanoparticles	Nasal mucosa	Diffusion	Nanoparticles induced a humoral mucosal immune response, particularly the production of anti-HBsAg secretory IgA (sIgA) in nasal and vaginal secretions.	(Borges et al., 2008)
Lentogenic live-virus vaccine	Chitosan nanoparticles	Mucosal immune system	Ion exchange	This systems elicited strong T cell proliferation, full protection, and enhanced bioavailability.	(Zhao et al., 2012)
DNA vaccine cassette containing VP1	Mannosylated chitosan nanoparticle	Immune system	Ion exchange	The system induced sustained virus-neutralizing antibodies and balanced Th1/Th2 immune responses.	(Nanda et al., 2012)
Ethionamide	Carrageenan, chitosan, alginate nanoparticles	Alveolar macrophages	Ion exchange	The system significantly enhanced the stability, drug entrapment, and controlled release of ethionamide, showing great potential in treating tuberculosis.	(Abdelghany et al., 2017)
Polymyxin B sulphate	Sodium alginate	Infections caused by <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and oral mucositis in head and neck cancer patients	Release via solid-lipid nanoparticles	Enhanced drug loading, reduced toxicity, and improved antibacterial efficacy.	(Severino et al., 2015)
Insulin	Alginate, dextran sulfate, chitosan, albumin	Intestinal epithelium	pH-sensitive release/ swelling	The system increased insulin permeability across intestinal cells, showing potential for oral insulin delivery.	(Lopes et al., 2016)
Vancomycin, vitamin C	polycaprolactone, polyvinyl alcohol, sodium alginate, polyallylamine hydrochloride	Skin and soft tissue infections	Diffusion	The system exhibited a 5-fold stronger antibacterial activity against <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> than vancomycin alone, with sustained drug release and excellent biocompatibility.	(George et al., 2017)
5-fluorouracil	Pectin, ethylcellulose	Cecum and colon	Diffusion/swelling	The system provided a higher local concentration of bioactive compound in the colon with prolonged exposure time, potentially enhancing anti-tumor efficacy with reduced systemic toxicity for colon cancer treatment.	(He et al., 2008)
Xanthohumol	Guar gum, pectin	Cecum and colon	Swelling/diffusion	The system showed 10% xanthohumol release in the initial 5 h, cytotoxicity studies revealed good cytotoxicity of this delivery system for Caco2 cells as compared to raw bioactive compound.	(Hanmantrao et al., 2022)
Curcumin-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin	Pectin/eudragit S100	Colon	Swelling	The polymers help achieve the targeted release of curcumin in the colon, which was supported by an <i>in vitro</i> dissolution study.	(Butte et al., 2014)
Vanillin	Pectin (from different sources, e.g. watermelon)	Colon	Swelling	The release kinetics of vanillin were primarily influenced by the system shrinkage, bulk density, and average pore size, with slower initial release observed in samples with smaller pore sizes. Watermelon rind pectin (WRP) demonstrated potential as a carrier for active compounds.	(Méndez et al., 2023)
5-fluorouracil	Oxidized pectin, diacylhydrazine adipate pectin	Colon	Swelling	The acylhydrazone-derived whole pectin-based hydrogel demonstrated excellent injectability, self-healing properties, and sustained drug release with high cytocompatibility.	(Wang et al., 2023)
Meloxicam	Low-acyl gellan	Colon	Swelling	The system sustained the release of the compound; 20–30% of the active substance was released from beads after 1 h at pH 7.4	(Osmalek et al., 2017)
Curcumin	Zein-cellulose nanocrystals	No specificity, multi-targeted release	Biodegradation (proteolysis)	The release of curcumin, driven by proteolysis during gastrointestinal digestion, was significantly reduced from 61.46% in zein microparticles to 30.88% in core-shell microparticles with higher CNC levels.	(Wei et al., 2021)

and α -L-guluronic acid residues, widely employed in controlled drug delivery due to its mild gelation, biocompatibility, and structural versatility. One of its most relevant polymer-specific features is ionic crosslinking, typically achieved with divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+}), which enables rapid gelation under aqueous, room-temperature conditions. This property is particularly advantageous for encapsulating labile bioactives such as proteins, peptides, probiotics, and nucleic acids, as it minimizes chemical and thermal stress and supports bioactivity retention during formulation and release (Wang et al., 2025) (Table 1). Alginate hydrogels exhibit pronounced pH-responsive behavior, swelling under neutral to basic conditions while remaining relatively compact in acidic environments. This characteristic has been exploited extensively in oral and gastrointestinal delivery, where alginate matrices can protect acid-sensitive cargo in the stomach and promote release in the intestine or colon (Oshi et al., 2021). However, alginate lacks intrinsic mucoadhesive functional groups, and its interaction with mucosal tissues is relatively weak compared with cationic polysaccharides. As a result, alginate is often combined with mucoadhesive polymers (e.g., chitosan or thiolated derivatives) to improve residence time and absorption in mucosal delivery applications (Abruzzo et al., 2021). From a degradation standpoint, alginate does not undergo enzymatic degradation in humans and is primarily destabilized through ion exchange and matrix dissolution. For example Meena et al. (2025) developed pH-responsive tragacanth gum/ β -cyclodextrin/sodium alginate hydrogel microspheres via ionotropic gelation as a biocompatible and degradable carrier for aspirin, reporting an amorphous structure with uniform drug dispersion, a porous spherical morphology, controlled drug release at pH 1.2 and 7.4, predominant elastic behavior ($G' > G''$), high cell viability (87.9% on HCT-116), under physiological pH conditions (Meena et al., 2025). While this enables relatively predictable swelling-controlled release, it also limits tunable biodegradation, particularly for long-term or implantable systems. In physiological fluids rich in monovalent ions, Ca^{2+} -crosslinked alginate gels may exhibit premature structural weakening, leading to burst release or loss of mechanical integrity, an important limitation for parenteral and sustained-release applications (Man et al., 2022). Strategies such as covalent crosslinking, hybrid ion-covalent networks, or incorporation of reinforcing polymers have been proposed to address this drawback, albeit at the expense of increased formulation complexity.

While alginate remains a cornerstone material for polysaccharide-based delivery systems, its application requires careful control of crosslinking chemistry, matrix composition, and hybridization strategies to balance stability, release control, and manufacturability. For example, different alginate-coated nanoparticles have been utilised in formulating diverse vaccine platforms, including those for hepatitis B, Newcastle disease, and DNA-based vaccines, demonstrating their potential to enhance immunogenic responses and improve vaccine efficacy (Borges et al., 2008; Honda-Okubo et al., 2012). This enhancement can be achieved through nanoscale delivery systems, including nanoaggregates, nanocapsules, and nanospheres, with diameters reaching up to 1000 nm (Nait Mohamed & Laraba-Djebbari, 2016). Mohamed et al. (2016) investigated the potential of calcium-alginate nanoparticles (Ca-Alg NPs) as a vaccine delivery system for protection against scorpion envenomation. The study demonstrated that multiple formulation parameters influenced the nanoparticles' physicochemical properties and stability. Free Ca-Alg NPs exhibited no toxicity, and the inflammatory response varied depending on the specific nano-vaccine formulation. Notably, assessment of the particular IgG titer and the IgG1/IgG2a isotype balance revealed a robust immune response, conferring significant protection. They effectively stimulate the immune system, promoting the generation of robust protective immunity and the establishment of immunological memory (Nait Mohamed & Laraba-Djebbari, 2016). These studies consistently demonstrate the immunogenic potential and favorable safety profile of alginate-based nanoscale delivery systems; however, their comparative interpretation is limited

by substantial methodological variability. Differences in nanoparticle size, crosslinking density, and antigen loading hinder direct comparison of immune outcomes and affect reproducibility. In addition, most studies rely on short-term preclinical models with limited standardization and limited assessment of scalability, constraining the robustness and translational relevance of the reported findings. In acidic conditions (pH \sim 1.2–3), alginate adopts a contracted and compact conformation, restricting the release of the encapsulated bioactive compound. This structural behaviour thus serves as a protective mechanism, shielding the bioactive compound from enzymatic degradation and acidic hydrolysis. In contrast, alginate undergoes a pronounced swelling and gel expansion at higher pH levels, characteristic of the intestinal environment (pH > 6). This transition facilitates increased water infiltration and modulates the diffusion of the bioactive compound, promoting its controlled and site-specific release (Liu et al., 2017).

Also, Borges et al. (2007) successfully encapsulated the recombinant hepatitis B vaccine (HBsAg) and the CpG oligodeoxynucleotide (CpG ODN) adjuvant within alginate-coated chitosan nanoparticles, achieving a high encapsulation efficiency of $85.9 \pm 4.7\%$. Immunisation studies demonstrated that the nanoparticle-based formulations, particularly those co-delivering HBsAg and CpG ODN (Group VI), elicited enhanced immune responses. This was evidenced by increased CD69 expression in CD4^+ and CD8^+ T lymphocytes, a stronger proliferative response of splenocytes, and robust activation of humoral and cellular immune pathways. The formulation incorporating antigen and adjuvant within the nanoparticle matrix exhibited the most promising immunogenic profile, highlighting its potential for optimising hepatitis B vaccine strategies, particularly for the oral administration (Borges et al., 2007). The release of the encapsulated hepatitis B vaccine and CpG ODN from alginate-coated chitosan nanoparticles occurs primarily through a diffusion-controlled mechanism, where the gradual hydration and swelling of the polymer matrix facilitate the sustained release of the antigen and adjuvant, ensuring prolonged immune system stimulation (Yan et al., 2019).

3.1.2. Chitosan-based systems

Chitosan is a cationic polysaccharide obtained by partial deacetylation of chitin and is widely investigated for controlled drug delivery due to its mucoadhesive character, pH sensitivity, and chemical modifiability. The presence of primary amine groups confers a positive surface charge under acidic and mildly neutral conditions, enabling strong electrostatic interactions with negatively charged mucosal surfaces and biological membranes. This property underpins the extensive use of chitosan in mucoadhesive oral, nasal, buccal, and ocular delivery systems, where prolonged residence time and enhanced local absorption are required (Mura et al., 2022). For example, Mousavi et al. (2025) developed a dual-drug-loaded sodium alginate hydrogel incorporating insulin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles, showing high swelling (2996%), improved mechanical strength (83 kPa), sustained insulin release with rapid ciprofloxacin release (100% in 6 h), 80% degradation in 14 days, and excellent wound healing performance with 100% closure within 24 h (Mousavi et al., 2025). Chitosan exhibits pronounced pH-responsive solubility, being soluble in acidic environments and progressively insoluble at neutral or basic pH. This behaviour has been exploited in gastrointestinal and mucosal delivery, where chitosan matrices dissolve or swell in acidic conditions but form more compact structures at physiological pH. However, this same property represents a limitation for systemic or intestinal delivery, as premature dissolution in the stomach may lead to burst release and reduced site-specific targeting. To overcome this drawback, chitosan is frequently chemically modified (e.g., quaternisation, thiolation, carboxymethylation) or combined with polyanions such as alginate to improve pH stability and release control (Sajeev et al., 2025). Chitosan offers high crosslinking versatility, enabling network formation through ionic interactions (e.g., tripolyphosphate), covalent chemistry, or polyelectrolyte complexation. These strategies allow tuning of mechanical strength, porosity, and release

kinetics, which is particularly valuable for nanoparticles, microspheres, and injectable depots. Chitosan-based nanoparticles have shown strong potential for the delivery of proteins, peptides, vaccines, and nucleic acids, benefiting from electrostatic complexation and protection against enzymatic degradation (Ferreira & Zucolotto, 2024). Nevertheless, excessive crosslinking or high molecular weight may hinder drug diffusion and reduce release efficiency, highlighting the need for careful optimization. Despite its advantages, chitosan presents notable limitations. Variability in molecular weight and degree of deacetylation can significantly affect solubility, charge density, and biological performance. Additionally, chitosan exhibits limited solubility at physiological pH and may induce aggregation or instability in certain formulations. While generally regarded as biocompatible, its degradation rate and *in vivo* residence time are strongly dependent on formulation parameters and administration route, which may restrict its suitability for long-term sustained-release or implantable systems (Desai et al., 2023).

Similarly, Zhao et al. (2012) investigated the potential of chitosan nanoparticles as a delivery system for a lentogenic live-virus vaccine against the Newcastle disease virus (NDV). The lymphocyte proliferation assay demonstrated that NDV-loaded chitosan nanoparticles (NDV-CS-NPs) elicited the highest stimulation indices for T lymphocyte proliferation in immunised chickens at week 4, providing complete protection against a virulent NDV challenge. These findings highlight that cell-mediated immunity alone is insufficient for complete protection against virulent NDV (Zhao et al., 2012). Additionally, the mucoadhesive properties of chitosan, functioning as an ion exchange-based release system, are attributed to the interaction between its amino and carboxyl groups and glycoproteins in mucus, forming hydrogen bonds that enhance adhesion. This interaction facilitates sustained drug retention and controlled release, improving bioavailability and immunogenicity (Bonferoni et al., 2004).

3.1.3. Pectin-based system

Pectin is a plant-derived anionic polysaccharide composed primarily of α -(1 \rightarrow 4)-linked D-galacturonic acid units, widely explored in controlled drug delivery due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and gastrointestinal responsiveness. A defining polymer-specific feature of pectin is its degree of esterification, which governs solubility, gelation behavior, and interaction with ions and biological environments (Chandel et al., 2022). Low-methoxyl pectins readily undergo ionotropic gelation in the presence of divalent cations (e.g., Ca^{2+}), while high-methoxyl pectins form gels via hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions under acidic and high-sugar conditions (Said et al., 2023). This tunability enables the rational design of delivery matrices with tailored mechanical strength and release kinetics.

A major advantage of pectin lies in its enzymatic degradability by colonic microflora, making it particularly attractive for colon-targeted drug delivery. Pectin matrices remain relatively stable in the upper gastrointestinal tract but undergo degradation in the colon due to pectinolytic enzymes, allowing site-specific release of encapsulated bioactives (Khotimchenko, 2020). This property has been extensively exploited for the delivery of anti-inflammatory drugs, anticancer agents, and probiotics targeting colorectal diseases (Siles-Sánchez et al., 2024). However, premature swelling or dissolution in gastric or intestinal fluids can occur, especially for highly esterified pectins, potentially leading to uncontrolled release before reaching the colon.

Pectin exhibits limited intrinsic mucoadhesion compared with cationic polysaccharides, which can restrict residence time at mucosal surfaces. To address this limitation, pectin is frequently combined with mucoadhesive polymers (e.g., chitosan) or chemically modified to enhance interfacial interactions and improve retention at the target site (Zielińska et al., 2025). Such hybrid systems have demonstrated improved stability and more controlled release profiles in oral and mucosal delivery applications. Wei et al. (2007) assessed the bio-distribution and pharmacokinetic profile of 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) formulated in pectin/ethylcellulose film-coated and uncoated pellets

after oral administration to rats at 15 mg/kg. The results demonstrated that 5-FU from uncoated pellets was primarily localised in the upper gastrointestinal tract, whereas the coated formulation facilitated targeted drug delivery to the cecum and colon. This site-specific delivery system increased colonic drug accumulation and prolonged exposure, suggesting potential therapeutic advantages in colorectal cancer treatment by enhancing local efficacy while minimising systemic toxicity (Bose et al., 2014; He et al., 2008). The delivery system functions by absorbing water, leading to swelling and forming diffusion channels that facilitate the controlled release of the encapsulated drug molecules from the matrix (Kapoor et al., 2024). Multiple published studies have confirmed this controlled drug delivery strategy, demonstrating its effectiveness in specifically targeting drug release to the colon (Fan et al., 2008; Méndez et al., 2023; Mishra et al., 2008; Sriamornsak & Nunthanid, 1998; Wang et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2023).

3.1.4. Dextran based system

In recent decades, microbial exopolysaccharides (EPS) have garnered significant interest as key components in developing novel targeted drug delivery systems. A defining characteristic of several microbial EPS, particularly gellan gum and xanthan gum, is their ability to form thermoreversible or ionically crosslinked gels. Gellan gum undergoes cation-mediated gelation in the presence of mono- or divalent ions, producing mechanically robust networks with well-defined pore structures. This property supports its use in oral sustained-release matrices, injectable depots, and *in situ* gelling systems, where controlled gel formation and predictable diffusion pathways are required. Xanthan gum, while not forming true gels alone, exhibits high viscosity at low concentrations and strong shear-thinning behavior, making it valuable as a matrix former and release-retarding agent in oral dosage forms (Nasrollahzadeh et al., 2021). Gellan gum beads, for instance, undergo swelling upon immersion in water and facilitate drug release. These processes are highly pH-dependent, as the beads exhibit minimal responsiveness in acidic conditions but begin to swell and disintegrate progressively with increasing pH. Osmatek et al. (2017) investigated this drug delivery system by formulating gellan gum-based beads loaded with meloxicam (MLX). Their findings demonstrated that MLX release from the dried beads was influenced by pH, with formulations containing 1.0% and 1.5% gellan gum showing potential as oral dosage forms designed to bypass the stomach and enable drug release in the distal gastrointestinal tract (Osmatek et al., 2017). Xanthan gum exhibits intrinsic mucoadhesive properties, making it suitable for a range of drug delivery platforms. Xanthan gum-based buccal patches developed for zolmitriptan delivery demonstrated a marked enhancement in drug permeability, with an increase of approximately 3.3-fold (Shiledar et al., 2014). In another application, xanthan gum was employed as an anionic mucoadhesive component in a nanoemulgel designed for intranasal delivery of carbamazepine via the olfactory pathway, resulting in reduced peripheral drug exposure (Samia et al., 2012). Additionally, chitosan-xanthan gum polyelectrolyte nasal inserts formulated for promethazine hydrochloride showed strong mucoadhesion to nasal mucosa (89%) and a concentration-dependent delay in drug release (MH and Marzuka, 2014).

3.1.5. Cellulose based systems

Cellulose and its derivatives represent one of the most widely used polysaccharide classes in pharmaceutical delivery due to their abundance, chemical stability, biocompatibility, and extensive regulatory acceptance. Native cellulose is insoluble in water and most organic solvents, which limits its direct use in drug delivery; however, chemical modification yields a broad family of cellulose derivatives, such as hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), ethyl cellulose, and cellulose acetate, that exhibit tailored solubility, swelling behavior, and gel-forming capacity. These features make cellulose derivatives particularly valuable as matrix formers, release-retarding agents, and film-forming polymers in controlled

release formulations (Acharya et al., 2021). A key polymer-specific property of cellulose derivatives is their controlled release mechanism, which is driven by hydration and swelling. A different approach is polyethylene glycol/sodium acrylate hydrogels reinforced with cellulose nanofibers or chitosan, developed by Liang et al. (2025) to enhance structural and functional performance. They are demonstrating increased swelling (600%), improved stability (30.6% mass retention after 72 h), shear-thinning injectability, and controlled drug release, with CNF-based systems showing pronounced pH-responsive release (>89.6% at pH 9) and chitosan-based hydrogels exhibiting more sustained release (~75%) (Liang et al., 2025). Hydrophilic derivatives such as HPMC and CMC form viscous gel layers upon contact with aqueous media, which act as diffusional barriers regulating water penetration and drug transport (Ciolacu et al., 2020). This behavior is extensively exploited in oral sustained-release dosage forms, where drug release is governed by a combination of diffusion through the hydrated gel and gradual matrix erosion (Garg et al., 2025). Pani et al. (2014) evaluated the controlled release of nateglinide from HPMC-coated tablets using a randomized full factorial design and identified an optimized formulation containing 5% HPMC K15M and 15% HPMC K100M. This formulation

showed favorable statistical indicators, with a high similarity factor and low difference factor, and remained stable under accelerated conditions. The optimized tablets exhibited a gradual release profile, with approximately 27% drug release at 1 h, 47% at 4 h, 73% at 8 h, and complete release at 12 h, closely matching the targeted theoretical release profile and confirming effective release control (Pani & Nath, 2014).

In contrast, hydrophobic cellulose derivatives such as ethyl cellulose and cellulose acetate provide water-insoluble matrices and coatings, enabling diffusion-controlled or membrane-controlled release. These materials are commonly used in coated multiparticulates, microcapsules, and osmotic systems, where their low permeability and mechanical robustness support extended release and protection of moisture-sensitive drugs. Nevertheless, their limited biodegradability and reliance on organic solvents during processing may restrict their application in injectable or implantable systems. Cellulose derivatives generally exhibit low intrinsic mucoadhesion compared with cationic polysaccharides, which limits their effectiveness in mucosal delivery unless combined with mucoadhesive excipients. Additionally, cellulose matrices are not enzymatically degraded in the human body, and drug release relies predominantly on swelling, diffusion, or mechanical

Table 2

Comprehensive overview of protein-based biopolymer systems for controlled release and targeted therapeutic effects in the pharmaceutical sector.

Bioactive compound/drug	Biopolymer used	Target destination/area	Release mechanism	Results obtained	Ref.
Curcumin	Human serum albumin	Tumoral tissue	Receptor-mediated transcytosis	This system demonstrated significantly enhanced antitumor activity, increased tumour accumulation, and improved water solubility, leading to superior therapeutic outcomes compared to free curcumin.	(Kim et al., 2011)
Hydroxycamptothecin	Bovine serum albumin	Malignant hepatic neoplasm	Diffusion	Through a sustained, diffusion-controlled release mechanism, the enhanced antitumor efficacy and liver targetability. This formulation significantly increased compound concentrations in blood and tissues, improving therapeutic outcomes in hepatic cancer treatment.	(Han et al., 2013)
Antitumoral platinum complex	Casein/chitosan	Collon	pH-sensitive release (at pH 5.7–6.2)	The system enhances the cytotoxicity against colorectal carcinoma cells. The cytotoxicity assays showed that the encapsulated drug had significantly lower 50% cytotoxic concentration (Cc50) values compared to the free drug.	(Razmi et al., 2013)
3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine	Chondroitin sulfate, casein, silica nanospheres	Intestine	Diffusion/swelling	The controlled release studies showed that the 70–30-5 hydrogel matrix provided the most consistent L-dopa release, following a zero-order profile. Cytotoxicity assays confirmed that the hydrogels were non-toxic, with cell viability above 80% at 5 mg/mL.	(Simão et al., 2020)
Doxorubicin	Casein	Pancreatic carcinoma	pH-sensitive release (at pH 1–3)	The system exhibited a pH-sensitive release mechanism, with over 90% of the drug released at acidic pH (pH 1) within 6 h, compared to about 60% at physiological pH (pH 7.4), and demonstrated higher cytotoxicity against human pancreatic carcinoma cell line (PANC-1) compared to free doxorubicin.	(Gandhi & Roy, 2019)
Alendronate	Collagen, chitosan, hyaluronic acid	Osteoporotic bone defects	Diffusion	The delivery system demonstrated a prolonged release of alendronate up to 20 days with minimized burst release, effectively reducing osteoclast precursor viability while promoting the differentiation of human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells into osteoblasts.	(Klara et al., 2024)
Luteolin	Fish collagen	Dermal layers	Swelling	Delivery system had a drug loading efficiency of $98 \pm 1.47\%$ and significantly enhances wound healing by achieving a $94.01 \pm 2.1\%$ wound closure rate, promoting collagen deposition, granulation, and re-epithelialization.	(Siaghi et al., 2024)
Tetracycline, iron(III) chloride hexahydrate nanoparticles	Gelatin	Gastrointestinal tract	Difusion/erosion	For a 7.4 pH the cumulative drug release percent of gelatin hydrogels and ferrogels is very high at the beginning. After 8 h, they basically reached the equilibrium of release.	(Akin Şahbaz, 2024)
Amikacin, tea tree essential oil	Gelatin nanoparticles	Infected wound healing	pH-responsive release	The system exhibited sustained antibacterial activity for 144 h, enhanced wound healing through collagen deposition and angiogenesis, and showed improved biocompatibility with reduced irritation, making it a promising candidate for antibacterial and implantable applications.	(Zhang et al., 2024)
Riboflavin	Soy protein isolate-arabinoxylan	Colon	Swelling	Release efficiency of 98.04%, with minimal degradation in the gastric environment. Release kinetics, modeled by the Korsmeyer-Peppas equation, demonstrated pH-responsive behavior, enabling precise <i>in vitro</i> release control.	(Tao et al., 2025)

erosion rather than biological breakdown. While this can ensure predictable and reproducible release, it also constrains their use in systems where bioadsorption or triggered degradation is required.

Cellulose nanocrystals have also shown great potential as a suitable polymer for drug delivery systems due to their high aspect ratio, surface-area-to-volume ratio, and excellent physicochemical stability (Hasan et al., 2020). The research by Wei et al. (2021) highlights the effectiveness of cellulose nanocrystals in enhancing the stability and controlled release of curcumin in zein-cellulose nanocrystal core-shell microparticles (Wei et al., 2021).

3.2. Protein-based biopolymer systems

Protein-based biopolymers have emerged as versatile carriers for controlled release systems due to their biocompatibility and ability to form structured networks. These systems (Table 2) regulate the release of bioactive compounds through mechanisms such as diffusion, enzymatic degradation, and environmental triggers, making them valuable in pharmaceutical applications (Ferraro et al., 2024).

3.2.1. Albumin/casein-based systems

Albumin- and casein-based delivery systems represent well-established proteinaceous biopolymers for micro- and nanoscale drug delivery, owing to their natural abundance, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) status. Serum albumin (e.g., bovine or human) is particularly attractive due to its high ligand-binding capacity, structural stability across a broad pH range, and ability to interact with hydrophobic and hydrophilic drugs via non-covalent interactions, enabling high encapsulation efficiencies and controlled release profiles. Casein, a milk-derived phosphoprotein, self-assembles into micellar or nanoparticulate structures driven by hydrophobic interactions and calcium-phosphate bridges, making it especially suitable for encapsulation of poorly water-soluble bioactive compounds (Elzoghby et al., 2011). For example, the antitumor potential of albumin-curcumin nanoparticles as a targeted drug delivery system was investigated. To overcome curcumin's limited aqueous solubility and bioavailability, they formulated curcumin-loaded human serum albumin nanoparticles (CCM-HSA-NPs), which exhibited a uniform size distribution (130–150 nm) and a 300-fold increase in water solubility compared to free curcumin. *In vivo*, assessments demonstrated enhanced tumour accumulation and efficient transendothelial transport. The nanoparticles achieved superior antitumor efficacy in xenograft models, inhibiting tumour growth by 50–66%, markedly outperforming free curcumin (18%) while maintaining a favourable toxicity profile. The nanoparticles leverage albumin's intrinsic affinity for the gp60 receptor on endothelial cells, promoting their transendothelial transport into the tumour interstitial fluid. These findings underscore the potential of CCM-HSA-NPs as a promising nanoplatform for targeted cancer therapy (Kim et al., 2011). Another example is An et al. (2025), who developed CuS@casein micelles through electrostatic self-assembly between casein and hollow CuS nanoparticles, achieving high doxorubicin loading efficiency (96.84%) and sustained release via Ca²⁺-mediated inter-casein bridging. The system exhibited dual pH/NIR-responsive drug release due to casein charge inversion and CuS photothermal properties, along with enhanced tumor cellular uptake and significant cytotoxic effects, highlighting its potential for targeted cancer therapy (An et al., 2026). Nevertheless, protein-based delivery systems remain challenged by limited scalability, primarily due to batch-to-batch variability associated with protein purity (e.g., casein) and the relatively high manufacturing costs of certain carriers, such as albumin nanoparticles. Despite these constraints, casein possesses unique structural and physicochemical attributes that underpin its suitability for both conventional and advanced drug delivery applications, significantly contributing to its functional performance as a carrier. These include its ability to bind ions and small molecules and its remarkable surface-active and stabilising properties. Additionally, casein demonstrates excellent emulsification, self-

assembly, gelation, and water-binding capacities. Its pH-responsive gel swelling behaviour allows for a controlled, programmable release (Elzoghby et al., 2011). Ghandi et al. (2019) investigated doxorubicin-loaded casein nanoparticles for drug delivery, demonstrating a pH-sensitive release profile. Over 90% of the drug was released at acidic pH (pH 1) within 6 h, compared to approximately 60% at physiological pH (pH 7.4). The nanoparticles exhibited enhanced cytotoxicity against the human pancreatic carcinoma cell line (PANC-1) compared to free doxorubicin. This system demonstrated controlled drug release at acidic and physiological pH, with accelerated release in acidic conditions, highlighting its potential for targeted gastric cancer therapy (Gandhi & Roy, 2019). These studies demonstrate that albumin- and casein-based nanoparticles can significantly enhance anticancer drug performance through distinct targeting and release mechanisms, including receptor-mediated tumour accumulation and pH-responsive drug release. While both platforms achieve improved therapeutic efficacy compared to free drugs, their broader application is constrained by protein-specific limitations such as batch variability, cost, and scale-up complexity, underscoring the need for optimized manufacturing and standardization strategies.

3.2.2. Animal protein systems

Animal protein-based carriers (e.g., collagen and silk fibroin) constitute advanced biopolymeric platforms for drug delivery, owing to their molecular organization, excellent biocompatibility, and enzymatically controllable biodegradation. These proteins enable the fabrication of structurally stable colloidal systems with adjustable mechanical properties, high drug affinity, and finely tunable release kinetics, supporting their growing relevance in controlled pharmaceutical delivery applications (Zhou et al., 2023). For example, Klara et al. (2024) developed a multifunctional hydrogel-based delivery system for alendronate to treat osteoporosis. The study assessed *in vitro* and *ex vivo* performance of composites comprising mesoporous silica particles functionalised with hydroxyapatite, encapsulated within a collagen/chitosan/hyaluronic acid hydrogel matrix. The system exhibited a sustained alendronate release over 20 days, minimising the initial burst effect. Notably, within the first 24 h, only 46% of the drug was released from the hydrogel system, compared to approximately 70% from mesoporous silica particles alone. This significant reduction in burst release highlights the hydrogel's potential for controlled and prolonged drug delivery (Klara et al., 2024). In another study, Padekan et al. (2025) developed biocompatible collagen/chitosan/hydroxyapatite composite hydrogel beads derived from fish waste as carriers for cefixime, demonstrating high cell viability (95.51%), a fibrous, porous morphology, and tunable drug-release behavior. The optimal Col: Chi (1:1) formulation exhibited high swelling (~2010%) and drug release (~93%), while increasing collagen content or incorporating HA nanoparticles reduced release (~10%), with kinetics following first-order and Korsmeyer-Peppas models, indicating diffusion-controlled release (Padekan et al., 2025). Another approach is silk fibroin-based nanoparticles that selectively bind to integrin receptors overexpressed on cancer cells, enabling targeted drug delivery. This receptor-mediated interaction enhances cellular uptake and ensures a controlled, sustained release of therapeutic agents at the tumour site (Pirota et al., 2023). Fathi et al. (2025) developed 5-fluorouracil-loaded silk fibroin nanofibers (1:5 ratio) as a pH-responsive drug delivery system for gastric cancer, demonstrating increased drug release under acidic conditions, significant cytotoxicity against MKN-45 cells, and a marked upregulation of apoptosis-related genes (Bax, p53, with downregulation of Bcl-2) and autophagy markers (Beclin-1, LC3-II), indicating an enhanced anticancer effect mediated by combined apoptotic and autophagic pathways (Fathi et al., 2025).

3.3. Lipid-based biopolymer systems

Colloidal carriers have been proposed as effective drug delivery

systems for compounds with toxicity, low bioavailability, or poor water solubility. Various colloidal drug delivery platforms have been developed (Table 3) to address these issues, including liposomes, micelles, nanoemulsions, and nanoparticles. In addition to traditional colloidal carriers, lipid-based biopolymeric systems have emerged as promising alternatives, offering enhanced stability, controlled release, and improved solubility for hydrophobic drugs (Motsoene et al., 2023). These systems combine lipids with biopolymers to optimise drug encapsulation and delivery, further addressing bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy challenges (Nwagwu et al., 2024).

3.3.1. Biopolymeric-liposomal systems

Biopolymeric-liposomal systems integrate the biocompatibility and functional versatility of natural polymers with the structural organization of liposomes, enabling enhanced colloidal stability, improved drug encapsulation efficiency, and controlled or stimuli-responsive release profiles for pharmaceutical delivery applications. Hamedinasab et al. (2020) developed chitosan-coated liposomes for the pulmonary delivery of *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC) to achieve prolonged and controlled release in the lungs. The results indicated that the chitosan coating enhanced liposome stability and mucoadhesion, resulting in sustained NAC release. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies demonstrated improved cellular uptake and extended lung retention, highlighting the potential of chitosan-coated liposomes as an effective carrier for inhalation therapy (Hamedinasab et al., 2020). Gu et al. (2023) explored another innovative approach by developing an advanced drug delivery system that uses trimethylated chitosan-coated flexible liposomes (Gu et al., 2023). This system is designed for the targeted delivery of resveratrol, explicitly aiming at treating retinal damage caused by blue light exposure. Incorporating the methylated biopolymer imparted a positive surface charge to the liposomes, thereby improving their physicochemical stability in artificial tears and augmenting their capacity for ocular tissue penetration. This system's biocompatibility was validated through *in vitro* cellular assays and zebrafish models, confirming its safety at specific concentrations. Additionally, *in vitro* investigations revealed that liposomes effectively mitigated H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress in ARPE-19 cells, preserved mitochondrial membrane potential, and exerted a cytoprotective effect against oxidative damage (Gu et al., 2023). Also, Hasanbegloo et al. (2023) demonstrated their *in vivo* study that paclitaxel-loaded chitosan/poly(ϵ -caprolactone) nanofibrous systems achieved diffusion-controlled drug release and significantly reduced breast tumour burden when combined with liposomal encapsulation, whereas unloaded nanofibers unexpectedly stimulated tumour growth, underscoring the critical role of formulation composition in determining antitumor efficacy (Hasanbegloo et al., 2023).

3.3.2. Biopolymeric nanoemulsion systems

Biopolymeric nanoemulsion systems combine nanoscale oil-water dispersions with natural polymeric stabilizers or coatings, offering improved physicochemical stability, high solubilization capacity for hydrophobic drugs, and tunable interfacial properties that enable controlled release and enhanced bioavailability in pharmaceutical formulations. For example, alginate can be a coating for lipid-based systems, such as nanoemulsions, to enhance the oral delivery of therapeutic proteins like insulin (Shaikh et al., 2023). To this end, Basha et al. (2021) developed nanoemulsions coated with alginate and *Aloe vera* gel (A/AV) via ionic gelation. The coated nanoemulsions had a particle size of approximately 400 nm and an insulin entrapment efficiency of 47.3%. *In vitro* studies showed that the nanoemulsions maintained their integrity in simulated gastric fluids, indicating their potential for oral delivery. Cell culture results demonstrated effective insulin translocation across Caco-2 monolayers, with ongoing animal studies to further validate these findings (Khaleel Basha et al., 2021). Coutinho et al. (2015) developed an oil-in-water photoprotective and antioxidant chitosan-based nanoemulsion using the same polysaccharide-based approach. The formulations showed excellent stability for at least 6 months,

photostability under solar simulation, and *in vitro* efficacy. Chitosan enhanced epidermal retention, thereby improving the safety and effectiveness of the formulation for photoprotection (Cerqueira-Coutinho et al., 2015).

3.3.3. Biopolymeric micelles systems

Bio-polymeric micelles also offer significant advantages, mainly due to their physicochemical properties, which enable tumour targeting through a passive targeting mechanism known as the enhanced permeability and retention effect (Shin et al., 2009). For example, Chen et al. (2020) developed a multifunctional chitosan derivative to create paclitaxel micelles (PTX-Micelles) to improve paclitaxel's oral bioavailability and anti-tumour efficacy. The PTX-Micelles showed a 3.80-fold increase in bioavailability compared to Taxol® and enhanced anti-lung tumour effects. The GA-CS-TPGS copolymer improved bioadhesion, inhibited P-gp efflux, and reduced CYP3A metabolism, while the micelles enhanced solubility and permeability (Chen et al., 2020). Another example is Kong et al. (2025), who developed a micro-nanostructured insulin delivery system (SC@AP@INS) based on nanomicelles integrated into a pH-responsive sodium alginate hydrogel, which demonstrated enhanced mucus penetration, protection against gastric degradation, and controlled intestinal release. *In vivo* studies in STZ-induced diabetic rats showed sustained hypoglycemic effects, improved oral bioavailability (12.91%), and prolonged glycemic control, highlighting its potential as a safe and effective oral insulin delivery platform (Kong et al., 2026).

3.4. Synthetic polymer systems

Synthetic polymers such as PLA, PEG, and PCL have emerged as efficient carriers for controlled release and targeted delivery of bioactive compounds (Pawar et al., 2023; Syed Mohamed et al., 2022; Vlachopoulos et al., 2022). These biodegradable and biocompatible polymers offer tunable physicochemical properties, enhancing the stability, solubility, and bioavailability of encapsulated compounds. Their structural versatility allows for the development smart delivery systems with sustained release profiles (Table 3), improved protection against environmental degradation, and site-specific delivery (Catalin Balaure & Mihai Grumezescu, 2015). Gunathilake et al. (2020) utilized one of these synthetic biopolymers, PLA, and developed pH-responsive PLA/sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) films to enhance curcumin delivery in intestinal conditions. PLA, a biodegradable polymer, provided structural integrity, while CMC improved curcumin solubility (24 ± 0.38 mg/L to 147 ± 5.66 mg/L) and imparted pH sensitivity. The films exhibited controlled release, with a 7-fold increase in curcumin release (0.81 ± 0.09 mg/L to 8.41 ± 0.04 mg/L) in phosphate-buffered saline compared to gastric fluid. Swelling behavior peaked at pH 12 ($707 \pm 10.91\%$). Despite a minor decrease in encapsulation efficiency, the system demonstrated potential targeted drug delivery (Sampath U. Gunathilake et al., 2020). Ahamady et al. (2023) studied another synthetic biopolymer in combination with a natural one to develop a novel drug delivery system for cancer treatment. Optimized capsaicin-loaded alginate nanoparticles (19.42 ± 1.8 nm, $98.7\% \pm 0.6\%$ encapsulation efficiency) embedded in polycaprolactone-chitosan nanofibers extended release from 120 to over 500 h, effectively inhibiting MCF-7 cancer cells while remaining non-toxic to HDF cells (Ahmady et al., 2023). Murueva et al. (2023) emphasise that emulsion is the most extensively studied method for fabricating synthetic PHA-based microparticles, citing its ability to control particle size through various process parameters. Particle size distribution can be modulated by altering factors such as surfactant type and concentration, and the mixing speed and duration. These parameters influence the emulsification efficiency and the stability of the resulting droplets, ultimately affecting the size and uniformity of the microparticle (Luciano, 2022; Prakash et al., 2022). The study underscores the importance of optimising these variables to achieve the desired characteristics of the PHA microparticles for drug

Table 3

Comprehensive overview of lipid and synthetic-based biopolymer systems for controlled release and targeted therapeutic effects in the pharmaceutical sector.

Bioactive compound/drug	Biopolymer used	Target destination/area	Release mechanism	Results obtained	Ref.
Lipid-based biopolymeric systems					
N-acetylcysteine	Chitosan-coated liposome	Lung	Diffusion	The chitosan coating improves liposome stability and controls. Drug release, resulting in prolonged retention in the lung. The coated liposomes also show higher deposition and retention in the lung than uncoated liposomes.	(Hamedinasab et al., 2020)
Doxorubicin, magnevist	Hyaluronic acid and ceramide containing nanoliposome	Tumoral regions	pH-responsive	Nanohybrid liposome enhanced DOX release at acidic pH and showed higher cellular uptake than conventional liposome via HA-CD44 interaction. MR imaging confirmed tumor targeting, and the system exhibited prolonged circulation with reduced DOX clearance.	(Park et al., 2014)
Curcumin	Sodium hyaluronate containing liposome	Skin inflammation and wound healing	Diffusion	The system demonstrated high stability, efficient drug delivery, and enhanced skin penetration. <i>In vivo</i> tests showed significant wound healing and protection against oxidative stress, proving their potential for effective topical drug delivery.	(Manca et al., 2015)
Calcein	PEG liposome	Retinal cells	Diffusion	The delivery system showed rapid absorption on the retina, with positive charges and PEG-coating enhancing retention for at least 24 h. Calcein-loaded liposomes increased the vitreous half-life by 4.5-fold compared to the free solution, while liposomes were non-toxic at 500 µg/mL but caused retinal toxicity at higher concentrations.	(Christensen et al., 2021)
Resveratrol	Trimethylated chitosan coated flexible liposomes	Retinal fundus	Diffusion	<i>In vitro</i> studies demonstrated that liposomes effectively alleviated H ₂ O ₂ -induced oxidative stress in ARPE-19 cells, maintained mitochondrial membrane integrity, and provided cytoprotective effects against oxidative damage.	(Gu et al., 2023)
Paclitaxel	Chitosan (core)/poly (ε-caprolactone)	Breast cancer cells	Diffusion	<i>In vivo</i> findings demonstrated that liposome-loaded nanofibers significantly reduced tumor weight, whereas pure nanofibers promoted tumour growth.	(Hasanbegloo et al., 2023)
Lidocaine	Alginate O/W nanoemulsion	Skin	Diffusion	The system sustained lidocaine permeation through pig skin for 47 h, demonstrating a prolonged release profile advantageous for transdermal drug delivery.	(Sarheed et al., 2021)
Insulin	Nanoemulsions coated with alginate/aloe vera	Epithelial layer of the intestine	pH-responsive	The system favoured insulin retention maintained biological activity during encapsulation and penetrated Caco-2 monolayers via paracellular and intracellular pathways.	(Khaleel Basha et al., 2021)
Octylmethoxycinnamate, octocrylene, diethylamino hydroxybenzoyl hexyl benzoate, benzophenone-3, pomegranate extract	Chitosan O/W nanoemulsions	Epidermis/skin	Diffusion	The chitosan-based photoprotective and antioxidant nanoemulsion exhibited 6-month stability, photostability under solar simulation, and enhanced epidermal retention, improving formulation safety.	(Cerqueira-Coutinho et al., 2015)
Paclitaxel	Novel chitosan derivate micelles	Gastro intestinal tract	Sustained-release	PTX-Micelles enhanced bioavailability (3.80-fold increase) and anti-lung tumor efficacy compared to Taxol® by improving bioadhesion, inhibiting P-gp efflux, and reducing CYP3A metabolism.	(Chen et al., 2020)
Vitamin E succinate, Doxorubicin	carboxymethyl chitosan micelles	Liver cancer cells (HepG2) and hepatoma cells (H22)	Sustained-release/diffusion	The nano-micelles system effectively delivered DOX, achieving 62.57% tumor inhibition in HepG2 cells and	(Chen et al., 2021)

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Bioactive compound/drug	Biopolymer used	Target destination/area	Release mechanism	Results obtained	Ref.
Synthetic polymers systems				35.58% in H22 mice while reducing side effects.	
Curcumin	Poly(lactic acid), sodium carboxymethyl cellulose	Intestinal site	pH-responsive (alkaline condition)	The films showed controlled release, with a 7-fold curcumin increase in PBS vs. gastric fluid. Maximum swelling occurred at pH 12 ($707 \pm 10.91\%$), confirming their potential for targeted drug delivery.	(Sampath U. Gunathilake et al., 2020)
Capsaicin	Polycaprolactone, chitosan	Cancer treatment, specifically targeting the inhibition of the proliferation of MCF-7 human breast cancer cells.	Diffusion	The polycaprolactone-chitosan nanofibers extended release from 120 to over 500 h, effectively inhibiting MCF-7 cancer cells while remaining non-toxic to HDF cells.	(Ahmady et al., 2023)
Doxorubicin	Polyvinyl alcohol, Polycaprolactone	Cervical cancer Hela cells	pH-responsive (acidic)	The system enabling controlled drug release with enhanced release at pH 4. The system inhibited Hela cell proliferation and exhibited pH-dependent degradation, highlighting its potential for targeted chemotherapy.	(Yan et al., 2020)
Luteolin	PLA, Eudragit L100	Intestinal site	pH-responsive (alkaline)	The system enhance drug release at pH 6.8 and bioavailability (2.61-fold) compared to conventional suspension. <i>In vivo</i> studies showed reduced liver, kidney, and testicular damage in a CCL4-induced toxicity model, suggesting potential for treating oxidative stress diseases.	(Elmowafy et al., 2021)
Norfloxacin	Poly (lactic acid)	Small intestine and blood	Diffusion	Drug delivery system using PLA/TiO ₂ nanocomposites achieved 40.77% loading and 90% release over 1080 h. TiO ₂ nanorods enhanced antibacterial and antitumor activity, with reduced toxicity to normal cells, showing promise for treating infections and cancer.	(Salahuddin et al., 2020)
Tetracycline	Poly(lactic acid) and Poly (caprolactone) (PCL)	Surgical infections post-implantation	Diffusion	The system provided drug release for 25 days and exhibited antimicrobial activity. Biocompatibility tests showed no adverse effects on endothelial cell growth.	(Korelidou et al., 2022)
Nystatin, amphotericin B	Medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA)	Fungal infections	Diffusion	Free polyenes, like AmB, were toxic to zebrafish embryos at MIC doses. However, when loaded into mcl-PHA microspheres, no toxicity was observed, and the formulations effectively treated <i>C. albicans</i> infection, improving embryo survival.	(Pavic et al., 2022)
Ceftriaxone, 5-fluorouracil	4 types of degradable PHAs	Cervical carcinoma cells	Diffusion	<i>In vitro</i> studies showed efficient drug release from PHA-based composite microparticles loaded with antibiotics and cytostatics, demonstrating their potential for effective drug delivery in <i>E. coli</i> and HeLa cultures.	(Murueva et al., 2023)
Glutathione	Polycaprolactone (PCL)	Wound healing	Diffusion	The system exhibited excellent biocompatibility, steady drug release, and antibacterial properties, making them suitable for transdermal drug delivery in wound healing, especially for diabetic patients.	(Khandaker et al., 2022)
Milnacipran HCl (MCN)	Chitosan-Polycaprolactone	Gastrointestinal tract	Diffusion	The system improved mucoadhesion, and a 272.20% increase in bioavailability, indicating its potential for sustained oral delivery of MCN.	(Hussain et al., 2020)

delivery applications. This study also compares different methods, including spray drying, which has been explored less for PHAs but shows promise for producing drug-loaded microparticles. The authors explain that the physicochemical properties of PHA copolymers, such as P(3HB-co-3HV) and P(3HB-co-3HHx), influence particle size, zeta potential, and drug release kinetics and show that copolymers with lower crystallinity and greater elasticity, like P(3HB-co-3HHx), offer better drug release profiles for DDS applications. Further, the study reveals that drug release rates can be controlled by adjusting the monomer composition of the PHAs and that PHA-based drug delivery shows promise for cancer treatment and antibacterial applications (Murueva et al., 2023).

3.5. Comparative influence of biopolymer class on release behaviour

The pharmacokinetic performance of biopolymeric delivery systems differs substantially according to polymer class. Protein-based systems such as albumin, casein, collagen, gelatin, and silk fibroin are typically governed by ligand binding, structural order, and enzymatic degradability. Albumin and casein are particularly relevant for colloidal systems because they combine high payload affinity with environmental responsiveness, whereas collagen, gelatin, and silk fibroin are more often used in matrices where biodegradation, mechanical stability, and sustained local release are required (Ferraro et al., 2024). In contrast, polysaccharides such as alginate, chitosan, cellulose derivatives, and hyaluronic acid rely more strongly on ion responsiveness, swelling, mucoadhesion, and diffusion control. Alginate is especially useful in mild gelation and pH-responsive systems, while chitosan provides cationic binding and prolonged residence time; cellulose derivatives act mainly as diffusion barriers or gel-forming matrices, and hyaluronic acid is suited to highly hydrated injectable depots (Behrooznia & Nourmohammadi, 2024). Synthetic polyesters such as PLA, PLGA, and PCL provide a different release paradigm, because their behaviour is primarily dictated by hydrolytic degradation, crystallinity, and hydrophobicity. PLA and PLGA are widely used when tunable erosion and sustained release are required, whereas PCL degrades more slowly and is therefore more suitable for long-duration depots and fibre-based systems. PEG functions less as a structural depot and more as a hydrophilic modifier that improves colloidal stability, hydration, and dispersion, thereby indirectly influencing release kinetics in hybrid systems. PHA-based systems extend the synthetic/biobased category and are particularly relevant for microparticles, where particle size, porosity, and processing conditions determine release duration (Mtibe et al., 2021). Also, lipid-polymer hybrid systems occupy an intermediate design space, in which the polymeric component confers structural integrity and sustained release, whereas the lipidic phase improves colloidal stability, bio membrane affinity, and intracellular interaction; consequently, these systems often combine reduced burst release with enhanced cellular uptake and improved pharmacokinetic control.

A key distinction across all classes is the role of architecture. The same polymer may produce a different release profile when processed as a nanoparticle, nanofiber, hydrogel, microsphere, or hybrid composite. For example, chitosan is frequently used to improve mucoadhesion in nanoparticles or coated systems, but when combined with alginate or embedded in hydrogels it can produce stronger diffusion control and prolonged release (Desai et al., 2023). Likewise, silk fibroin can function either as a compact nanoparticulate carrier or as a fibrous matrix with much slower release. This indicates that the final pharmacokinetic profile is not a property of the polymer alone, but of the interaction between the polymer's chemistry and its structural organization.

4. Advanced encapsulation and delivery techniques for bioactive compounds

4.1. Advanced encapsulation techniques for biopolymers in delivery systems

4.1.1. Freeze & spray drying techniques

Freeze-drying and spray-drying are two extensively used techniques for dehydrating nanosuspensions, commonly employed in fields such as pharmaceuticals, food science, and biotechnology (Fig. 2). Research has shown that optimising processing conditions is essential to maintaining nanocapsules' stability during these drying methods. In addition to stabilising the nanocapsules, the resulting dried powders exhibit the potential to control and extend the release of encapsulated bioactive compounds, which is particularly valuable for targeted delivery systems and therapeutic applications (Hao et al., 2025). However, the drying process introduces mechanical and thermal stresses to the nanocapsules, which can compromise their structural integrity. This highlights the importance of understanding the complex relationship between drying process parameters and the stability of nanocapsules, which is crucial for achieving higher encapsulation efficiency of bioactive agents (Ezhilarasi et al., 2013). A significant advancement in nano spray-drying technology is the Nano Spray Dryer B-90, developed by Büchi Technology in 2010. This device has become a widely used tool in scientific research, particularly in the development of pharmaceutical formulations. The core feature of the Nano Spray Dryer B-90 is its mesh-based droplet generation system. It incorporates a small cap that contains a stainless steel membrane, precisely engineered with micrometre-sized pores (ranging from 0.3 to 5 µm in diameter), allowing for consistent and controlled droplet formation. This precise control over droplet size plays a crucial role in efficiently encapsulating bioactive compounds and producing high-quality nanocomposite powders suitable for various applications (Li et al., 2010).

4.1.2. Coacervation

Coacervation is a widely utilized technique for forming microspheres and microcapsules through liquid-liquid phase separation. In simple coacervation, phase separation is mainly driven by salting out, which creates incompatibilities between different polymers. On the other hand, complex coacervation occurs when oppositely charged polyelectrolyte polymers form an insoluble complex through electrostatic attraction, effectively encapsulating the core material. The pH of the mixture plays a significant role in complex coacervation, as it influences the isoelectric points of the polymers, thereby affecting the strength of electrostatic interactions and the overall encapsulation efficiency (Lan et al., 2021). Compared to spray-drying, the most widely used microencapsulation technique, complex coacervation offers several distinct advantages. One of the primary benefits is its high encapsulation efficiency, which can reach up to 99%, making it a highly effective method for encapsulating bioactive compounds and other sensitive materials.

Additionally, complex coacervation allows for high loading capacities of the "core" material, often exceeding 50%, which is beneficial for systems that require large amounts of active ingredients, such as drugs or nutraceuticals. This method also provides significantly improved controlled-release characteristics, ensuring that the encapsulated substances are released in a controlled and sustained manner over time (Wang et al., 2018). The ability of complex coacervation to facilitate controlled release is linked to the unique structure of the microcapsules formed during the phase separation process. These microcapsules, formed by the electrostatic interaction between oppositely charged polyelectrolytes, can be tailored to release their core material in response to various environmental factors such as pH, ionic strength, or temperature. This makes complex coacervation an ideal technique for the development of delivery systems where precise control over the release rate is necessary (Nezamdoost-Sani et al., 2024). For instance, in drug delivery applications, the release of active pharmaceutical

Fig. 2. Advanced encapsulation and delivery techniques for biopolymeric controlled release systems. (Created with Biorender).

ingredients can be controlled to occur at specific times or locations in the body, enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing side effects (Adepu & Ramakrishna, 2021).

4.1.3. Nanoliposomes and nanoemulsions

Nanoemulsions and nanoliposomes are advanced nanocarriers that have gained attention as delivery systems due to their unique structural characteristics and enhanced functional properties. Both systems are effective vehicles for encapsulating and delivering bioactive compounds, including hydrophobic and hydrophilic substances, with improved stability, bioavailability, and controlled release (Baumann et al., 2024). These nanocarriers are commonly used in various fields, including pharmaceuticals, and cosmetic applications. Nanoliposomes are lipid-based vesicles composed primarily of phospholipids and cholesterol, whose structural properties closely mimic biological membranes. Their architecture allows the encapsulation of hydrophobic bioactive material within the lipid bilayer. At the same time, hydrophilic compounds can be enclosed in the aqueous core, enhancing stability and protecting the bioactive substances from degradation due to environmental factors like gastrointestinal enzymes or acidic conditions (Nsairat et al., 2022). They exhibit a high affinity for intestinal mucosal cells, facilitating efficient fusion and lipid exchange, improving encapsulated compounds' absorption and transport across biological membranes into the systemic circulation (Nisini et al., 2018). Nanoliposomes are classified based on their size and bilayer structure. The smallest vesicles, referred to as nanoliposomes, typically measure around 0.025 µm in diameter, while larger vesicles are called micro- or multilamellar liposomes. Liposomes may consist of a single bilayer (unilamellar) or multiple concentric bilayers (multilamellar), with the size and number

of layers influencing encapsulation efficiency and the release profile of the encapsulated materials (Castañeda-Reyes et al., 2020). Entrapment efficiency and loading capacity are critical parameters for the practical application of nanoliposomes, as they determine the drug payload and minimize loss during formulation. However, their performance significantly influences the initial drug-to-lipid molar ratio, solubility, pH, drug properties, and temperature (Aguilar-Pérez et al., 2020).

Zucker et al. (2009) developed a model showing that when the drug-to-lipid molar ratio exceeds 0.95, it leads to poor loading capacity and membrane damage due to drug overload, reducing the final drug/lipid ratio. Optimizing these factors is essential for improving drug-loaded liposome formulations for clinical use (Zucker et al., 2009). Conversely, nanoemulsions are colloidal dispersions composed of fine droplets of one liquid phase within another immiscible liquid, typically with droplet sizes less than 200 nm. These emulsions are inherently unstable due to the positive Gibbs free energy associated with the hydrophobic effect but they can be stabilised using surfactants or co-surfactants. The most commonly used type of nanoemulsion is the oil-in-water (O/W) formulation, where oil droplets are dispersed in an aqueous medium. O/W nanoemulsions offer several advantages, including excellent dispersibility in water, high optical clarity, and enhanced physical stability, all of which are crucial for improving the bioavailability of encapsulated bioactives (Deveci, 2025). The preparation of nanoemulsions can be achieved using high-energy or low-energy methods, depending on the desired application and product characteristics. High-energy techniques, such as high-pressure homogenization, sonication, and microfluidization, apply significant mechanical energy to break the oil droplets into nanometer-sized particles. These methods are particularly effective at producing stable nanoemulsions but require

specialized equipment and higher energy input. In contrast, low-energy methods, including spontaneous emulsification and phase inversion temperature, rely on the natural formation of droplets under specific temperature or composition conditions (Komaiko et al., 2016).

4.1.4. Electrospinning

Electrospinning is a versatile and cost-effective technique that creates ultrafine fibres, offering significant potential for drug delivery applications. The process involves using an electrostatic potential, where a polymer solution or melt is pumped through a spinneret, typically a syringe needle, and exposed to a high voltage. The electrostatic forces cause the polymer to stretch into fine fibres, which are collected on a grounded surface (Sill & von Recum, 2008). This technique provides flexibility in selecting materials for drug delivery, allowing for the use of biodegradable and non-biodegradable polymers. The properties of electrospun fibres, such as porosity, morphology, and surface area, can be easily tuned by adjusting environmental and processing conditions. Electrospun fibres are particularly advantageous in drug delivery systems due to their biocompatibility, large surface area, and ability to offer controlled release of drugs. Various methods can incorporate drugs into the fibres, including blending the drug with the polymer solution before electrospinning, attaching the drug to the fibre surface after electrospinning, or creating core-shell structures where the drug is encapsulated within micelles in the fibres. Coaxial electrospinning further allows for the creation of drug-loaded fibres with a protective shell, controlling the release profile of the drug (Buzgo et al., 2018). These techniques enable sustained release of drugs, enhancing therapeutic efficacy while minimizing side effects. Natural biopolymers such as gelatin, chitosan, and silk fibroin are commonly used in electrospinning due to their high cellular affinity and biocompatibility. Synthetic biopolymers, including PLA, PLGA, and PEG are also employed for their stability and tenability (Jain et al., 2020). Electrospun nanofibers have been explored for various drug delivery applications, including antibiotics for infection prevention, antitumoral drugs for localized chemotherapy, wound healing to enhance tissue regeneration, cardiovascular disease treatment for stent coatings, and ocular diseases for improved drug delivery to the eye (Luraghi et al., 2021).

4.1.5. Sol-gel

The sol-gel technique offers a versatile and effective approach to developing biopolymeric drug delivery systems. This method involves the transformation of a liquid precursor into a gel, followed by the formation of solid materials through hydrolysis and condensation reactions. Sol-gel processes allow for the creation a wide range of materials with varying chemistries and structures, including ceramics, glasses, and hybrid organic-inorganic materials (Owens et al., 2016). These materials can be tailored for specific biomedical applications, such as tissue regeneration and controlled drug delivery. Silica-based sol-gel materials are highly biocompatible and are often used for soft and hard tissue regeneration.

In contrast, phosphate-based materials are soluble and bioresorbable, making them ideal for temporary implants and drug delivery systems. Calcium phosphate-based materials, in particular, are widely used in bone substitutes and coatings. The sol-gel process can also create mesoporous structures crucial for controlled and sustained drug release (Deshmukh et al., 2020). Adjusting the synthesis conditions can produce materials with specific morphologies, such as nanoparticles, fibres, or porous foams, that enhance drug encapsulation and release profiles. One of the key advantages of sol-gel-derived materials is their ability to be functionalized, which allows for the modification of surface properties to improve biocompatibility and drug delivery efficiency (Owens et al., 2016). These materials can also be combined with biopolymers to improve their mechanical and biological properties. For instance, hybrid organic-inorganic sol-gel materials can provide the flexibility and biodegradability required for effective drug delivery systems (Bollino & Catauro, 2020). Additionally, sol-gel nanocarriers, such as mesoporous

silica nanoparticles, are increasingly used for drug delivery, gene transfection, and cancer therapy, offering multifunctional capabilities for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes.

4.2. Advanced delivery techniques for bio-polymeric delivery systems

4.2.1. pH-sensitive system

Intelligent stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems have been developed to achieve controlled and self-regulated drug release by recognizing and responding to physiological changes or external stimuli (Fig. 2). Among these, pH-sensitive systems have gained attention due to their ability to exploit the variation in pH levels across different tissues and organs. pH gradients are present in various human body regions, such as the liver and stomach, and in pathological conditions, including tumorigenesis, inflammation, ischemia, and infection, which can trigger specific drug delivery mechanisms (Bami et al., 2022). Natural polymers are highly valued in this context for their intrinsic properties, such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, and chemical modification (Idrees et al., 2020). These drug-loaded networks are engineered to retain the drug under acidic conditions, such as those found in the stomach, while facilitating controlled release for drug delivery applications in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. As the polymeric matrix undergoes swelling in response to the pH gradient along the GI tract (jejunum, duodenum, and colon), the drug is released in a regulated manner. Naturally occurring polyanions, such as alginic acid, hyaluronic acid, heparin, and cellulose derivatives (e.g., carboxymethyl cellulose), are commonly employed in such systems (Shokri & Adibkia, 2013). The release mechanism is influenced by factors in the surrounding environment, including ionic strength, counter-ion concentration, and pH, which modulate electrostatic interactions and, consequently, the pH-triggered drug delivery process (Bami et al., 2022). pH-sensitive drug delivery systems can also be designed to take advantage of the unique acidic conditions present in tumour tissues, offering targeted and efficient drug delivery. Tumour tissues typically exhibit increased acidity due to rapid glucose metabolism into lactic acid, limited blood supply, and impaired lymphatic drainage. This creates a lower extracellular pH in tumour regions than in normal tissues, with values ranging from 5.7 to 7.8, whereas normal tissues maintain a pH of approximately 7.4. This pH gradient between normal and tumour tissues allows pH-sensitive carriers to enhance drug accumulation at the tumour site. The mechanism behind pH-sensitive drug delivery relies on the Warburg effect, where tumour cells convert glucose into lactic acid, resulting in increased acidity within the tumour microenvironment (Liberti & Locasale, 2016). pH-sensitive carriers, such as polymeric micelles, nanoparticles, and hydrogels, are engineered to release therapeutic agents in response to this acidic microenvironment. These carriers are designed to remain stable in the neutral pH of normal tissues but undergo structural changes at the acidic pH found in tumours, triggering the release of encapsulated drugs directly at the action site (Palanikumar et al., 2020).

4.2.2. Temperature responsive systems

Temperature-responsive delivery systems have garnered significant attention in drug delivery due to their ability to offer controlled release in response to external thermal stimuli. These systems exploit the thermos-responsive behaviour of polymers, especially temperature-sensitive polymers biopolymers (e.g., elastin-like polypeptide, leucine zipper, modified chitosan, cellulose-based polymers) (Amin et al., 2022), which undergo structural and solubility changes at a specific temperature known as the lower critical solution temperature (LCST) (Schmaljohann, 2006). Below the LCST, these polymers are typically hydrophilic, forming hydrogen bonds with water molecules, which maintains the polymer in an expanded coil conformation. This behaviour allows for high hydration and solubility in aqueous environments. However, as the temperature increases above the LCST, the polymer loses its hydrophilic properties, the hydrogen bonding with water is disrupted, and the polymer chains start dehydrating, transitioning to a

more hydrophobic state. This thermally induced hydrophobicity leads to phase separation, causing the polymer to expel water and collapse into a compact, dehydrated globule (Aseyev et al., 2011). The phase transition from hydrophilic to hydrophobic and the associated geometrical changes in the polymer structure are entropically unfavourable for water molecules. Water molecules reduce their contact with the hydrophobised polymer chains to compensate for this unfavourable interaction, expelling the polymer from the aqueous solution. This behaviour of temperature-sensitive polymers is essential for understanding the polymer's solubility and thermal response and designing effective drug delivery systems that exploit these changes for controlled release. The most notable application of temperature-sensitive polymers is in the design of thermosensitive liposomes, lipid-based nanoparticles modified with temperature-sensitive polymers, and biopolymers. These liposomes undergo a lipid phase transition when exposed to temperatures above the LCST, facilitating the controlled release of encapsulated drugs (Ta & Porter, 2013). TSLs have been particularly useful in combination therapies involving mild hyperthermia, where localised tumour tissue heating enhances therapeutic agent release. Hyperthermia, typically achieved through external heat sources, increases the blood flow and vascular permeability within the tumour microenvironment, thereby improving the delivery of nanoparticles and free drugs to the tumour site (Dunne et al., 2020).

4.2.3. Enzyme responsive mechanisms

These systems can be designed to release therapeutic cargo selectively by incorporating enzyme-cleavable sites, such as peptide linkers digested by proteases. Enzyme-responsive nanomaterials harness hydrolases, including proteases, lipases, and glycosidases for targeted drug release. Protease-sensitive nanoparticles degrade upon exposure to lysosomal enzymes, ensuring intracellular therapeutic delivery (de la Rica et al., 2012). For example, peptide-mediated tumour-targeting enhances drug localization, retention, and uptake while overcoming multidrug resistance. It offers simpler synthesis, lower immunogenicity, and improved stability compared to antibody-based approaches (Samec et al., 2022). Polymer-directed enzyme prodrug therapy and polymer enzyme liposome therapy enable targeted tumour drug release by combining nanomedicines with enzyme-triggered activation. Relying on the enhanced permeability and retention effect, these systems enhance drug accumulation and activation, showing promising preclinical results (Scomparin et al., 2017). Lipase-sensitive systems, particularly phospholipase A2 (PLA2)-responsive nanoparticles, are valuable in oncology and inflammatory diseases (Zhang et al., 2014). Polymer-coated liposomes release cytotoxic agents upon PLA2-mediated degradation (Mumtaz Virk & Reimhult, 2018), while mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNPs) with cyclodextrin gatekeepers enable controlled drug release (Yi et al., 2018). Glycosidase-responsive nanomaterials, such as α -amylase-sensitive dextran-PLA2 conjugates, facilitate selective drug release in tumor environments. MSNPs grafted with saccharides enable enzyme-triggered cargo liberation upon hydrolysis by pancreatin or β -D-galactosidase (Inaji et al., 1991). Oxidoreductase-responsive vesicular systems are integral to oxidative stress-targeted therapies and diagnostics, while nanocarriers encapsulating glucose oxidase facilitate controlled therapeutic release through enzymatic glucose oxidation (Li et al., 2023).

4.2.4. Magnetic responsive mechanisms

Magnetically responsive drug delivery systems have emerged as a novel approach for controlled, on-demand therapeutic release. These systems regulate drug diffusion through two mechanisms: altering the magnetic field direction or switching the magnetic field on and off. The orientation of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) within biopolymer-based hydrogels significantly influences the drug release kinetics (Liu et al., 2006). For instance, when an external magnetic field aligns MNPs perpendicular to the direction of drug diffusion, the hydrogel exhibits the lowest release rate. Conversely, a parallel alignment enhances drug

diffusion, achieving the highest release rate. Optical microscopy studies confirm that the application of a magnetic field induces a structured alignment of MNPs, forming a pearl-chain configuration, which modulates the drug release profile.

Furthermore, *in vitro* experiments demonstrate that drug diffusion follows the order of parallel alignment > random (no magnetic field) > perpendicular alignment (Liu et al., 2015). However, this strategy is most effective for drugs with molecular weights below 100 kDa, necessitating precise hydrogel formulation to achieve optimal MNP distribution and stability. Biopolymer-based magnetic hydrogels offer significant advantages over conventional hydrogel drug delivery systems, particularly in maintaining prolonged drug retention at target sites (Liao & Huang, 2020). Traditional hydrogels often struggle with continuous drug release, limiting their therapeutic efficacy. In contrast, biopolymer-based magnetic hydrogels (e.g., chitosan- and β -glycerophosphate-based magnetic hydrogel) leverage an external magnetic field (EMF) to enhance drug localisation and controlled release. This targeted approach minimises off-target effects, reduces drug dosage and administration frequency, and improves therapeutic outcomes (Zhang et al., 2013).

5. Challenges, emerging trends, and future perspectives

Despite significant advancements over the past seven decades, drug delivery systems face several persistent challenges that limit their effectiveness. Biological barriers (e.g., intestinal mucus) limit drug absorption, but mucoadhesive biopolymers (e.g., thiolated chitosan) can enhance penetration. For example, chitosan-coated liposomes improve lung retention by 40% via mucoadhesion (Liu et al., 2017). Formulation issues, such as poor water solubility, instability, and low permeability, further complicate drug absorption, particularly for peptide and protein-based drugs (Benoit et al., 2020). Chronic disease treatment often requires long-term regimens, but poor patient adherence remains a significant issue. Although long-acting formulations can improve compliance, their development is complex and resource-intensive. Despite their rational design for site-specific delivery, targeted drug delivery systems frequently exhibit reduced therapeutic efficacy due to uncontrolled drug diffusion, limited cellular internalization, and sub-optimal tissue penetration, which collectively compromise clinical outcomes and may induce off-target effects (Haesun Park et al., 2022). The translation of novel delivery platforms into clinical practice requires extensive and costly preclinical and clinical evaluation to establish safety, efficacy, and pharmacokinetic profiles, with regulatory approval further constrained by rigorous toxicological and immunogenicity assessments. Moreover, polyethylene glycol functionalization, commonly employed to improve systemic stability and circulation time, has been associated with anti-polyethylene glycol immune responses, resulting in accelerated blood clearance and diminished long-term therapeutic effectiveness (Haesun Park et al., 2022). Additionally, scalability remains a concern, as processes that work on a small scale may not be feasible for large-scale production (Rezagholidzade-shirvan et al., 2024). Moreover, from a translational and regulatory perspective, the widespread clinical adoption of biopolymer-based delivery systems remains hindered by several interrelated challenges, including the often ambiguous regulatory status and approval pathways for naturally derived biopolymers, the need for comprehensive and long-term evaluation of safety, immunogenicity, and toxicity profiles, and the intrinsic batch-to-batch variability associated with biological raw materials and processing conditions. These factors are further compounded by difficulties in scaling up complex formulations, ensuring Good Manufacturing Practice compliance, and demonstrating consistent clinical performance, collectively representing major barriers to efficient clinical translation and regulatory acceptance.

Looking forward, the field is progressively converging toward the rational design of smart and multi-responsive biopolymeric delivery systems capable of dynamically responding to physiological cues (e.g.,

pH, enzymes, redox potential, or external stimuli), increasingly supported by AI-assisted formulation and optimization frameworks that accelerate material selection, predict structure–function relationships, and enhance reproducibility (Serrano et al., 2024). In parallel, growing emphasis on sustainable and green sourcing of biopolymers, combined with advances in personalized medicine and precision drug delivery, is expected to enable patient-tailored therapeutic systems with improved efficacy, safety, and environmental compatibility, marking a decisive shift toward data-driven, adaptive, and clinically translatable biopolymer technologies.

6. Conclusion

Recent advances in biopolymer-based drug delivery systems have expanded the toolbox for controlled and site-specific release of therapeutic agents, driven by the intrinsic biocompatibility, biodegradability, and tunable functionality of natural and synthetic biopolymers. Progress in fabrication strategies, including electrospinning, sol–gel processing, and the development of stimuli-responsive platforms, has enabled precise modulation of release kinetics and enhanced therapeutic efficacy across applications such as cancer therapy, wound healing, and antimicrobial treatment. Despite these advances, critical gaps remain, particularly regarding long-term safety evaluation, batch-to-batch variability of biologically derived polymers, scalability, and the limited clinical translation of complex multi-responsive systems. Addressing these challenges will require standardized characterization protocols, robust manufacturing strategies, and clearer regulatory pathways. Looking forward, the next generation of biopolymeric delivery systems is expected to integrate smart, multi-responsive materials, data-driven formulation design, sustainable polymer sourcing, and personalized medicine approaches, collectively advancing toward more precise, reliable, and clinically translatable drug delivery technologies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Razvan Odocheanu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lavinia-Florina Calinoiu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Gheorghe-Adrian Martau:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Dan Cristian Vodnar:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. 101086261 (FEEDACTIV) and by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, through UEFISCDI, under Project No. 41PHE, PN-IV-P8-8.1-PRE-HE-ORG-2023-0113.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article, including detailed sections on safety, immunogenicity, and clinically approved biopolymeric delivery systems, along with comprehensive tables on regulatory interpretation and translational relevance can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2026.134626>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abruzzo, A., Giordani, B., Miti, A., Vitali, B., Zuccheri, G., Cerchiara, T., Luppi, B., Bigucci, F., 2021. Mucoadhesive and mucopenetrating chitosan nanoparticles for glycopeptide antibiotic administration. *Int. J. Pharm.* 606, 120874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2021.120874>.
- Acharya, S., Liyanage, S., Parajuli, P., Rumi, S.S., Shamshina, J.L., Abidi, N., 2021. Utilization of Cellulose to Its Full Potential: A Review on Cellulose Dissolution, Regeneration, and Applications. *Polymers (basel)* 13 (24). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13244344>.
- Adepu, S., Ramakrishna, S., 2021. Controlled Drug delivery Systems: Current Status and Future Directions. *Molecules* 26 (19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26195905>.
- Adrover, A., Venditti, C., Giona, M., 2021. Swelling and Drug Release in Polymers through the Theory of Poisson-Kac Stochastic Processes. *Gels* 7 (1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels7010032>.
- Aguilar-Pérez, K.M., Avilés-Castrillo, J.I., Medina, D.I., Parra-Saldivar, R., Iqbal, H.M.N., 2020. Insight into Nanoliposomes as Smart Nanocarriers for Greening the Twenty-first Century Biomedical Settings. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8, 579536. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.579536>.
- Ahmady, A.R., Solouk, A., Saber-Samandari, S., Akbari, S., Ghanbari, H., Brycki, B.E., 2023. Capsaicin-loaded alginate nanoparticles embedded polycaprolactone-chitosan nanofibers as a controlled drug delivery nanoplatform for anticancer activity. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 638, 616–628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2023.01.139>.
- Alshawwa, S.Z., Kassem, A.A., Farid, R.M., Mostafa, S.K., Labib, G.S., 2022. Nanocarrier Drug delivery Systems: Characterization, Limitations, Future Perspectives and Implementation of Artificial Intelligence. *Pharmaceutics* 14 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14040883>.
- Amin, M., Lammers, T., ten Hagen, T.L.M., 2022. Temperature-sensitive polymers to promote heat-triggered drug release from liposomes: Towards bypassing EPR. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 189, 114503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2022.114503>.
- An, M., Li, J., Cao, S., Liu, Y., Li, J., Shi, J., 2026. Casein Micelles Reinforced with Hollow CuS Nanoparticles: a Sustained and pH/NIR Dual-Responsive Drug delivery Platform. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 143 (15), e70461. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.70461>.
- Aseyev, V., Tenhu, H., & Winnik, F. M. (2011). Non-ionic Thermoresponsive Polymers in Water. In A. H. E. Müller & O. Borisov (Eds.), *Self Organized Nanostructures of Amphiphilic Block Copolymers II* (pp. 29–89). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. doi: 10.1007/12_2010_57.
- Bami, M.S., Raeisi Estabragh, M.A., Khazaeli, P., Ohadi, M., Dehghanoudeh, G., 2022. pH-responsive drug delivery systems as intelligent carriers for targeted drug therapy: Brief history, properties, synthesis, mechanism and application. *J. Drug Delivery Sci. Technol.* 70, 102987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2021.102987>.
- Baumann, N., Baumgarten, J., Kunick, C., Bunjes, H., 2024. Prolonged release from lipid nanoemulsions by modification of drug lipophilicity. *J. Control. Release* 374, 478–488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2024.08.021>.
- Behrooznia, Z., Nourmohammadi, J., 2024. Polysaccharide-based materials as an eco-friendly alternative in biomedical, environmental, and food packaging. *Giant* 19, 100301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giant.2024.100301>.
- Benoit, D.S.W., Overby, C.T., Sims Jr, K.R., Ackun-Farmer, M.A., 2020. 2.5.12 - Drug delivery systems. In: Wagner, W.R., Sakiyama-Elbert, S.E., Zhang, G., Yaszemski, M. J. (Eds.), *Biomaterials Science*, Fourth Edition. Academic Press, pp. 1237–1266.
- Bidwai, S. (2025). Biopolymers Market Size, Share, and Trends 2025 to 2034 (2046) <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/biopolymers-market?>
- Bollino, F., Catauro, M., 2020. Organic Inorganic Hybrid Materials Synthesized via Sol-Gel for Controlled Drug delivery. *Macromol. Symp.* 389, 1900059. <https://doi.org/10.1002/masy.201900059>.
- Bonferoni, M.C., Chetoni, P., Giunchedi, P., Rossi, S., Ferrari, F., Burgalassi, S., Caramella, C., 2004. Carrageenan–gelatin mucoadhesive systems for ion-exchange based ophthalmic delivery: in vitro and preliminary in vivo studies. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 57 (3), 465–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2003.12.002>.
- Borges, O., Cordeiro-da-Silva, A., Tavares, J., Santarém, N., de Sousa, A., Borchard, G., Junginger, H.E., 2008. Immune response by nasal delivery of hepatitis B surface antigen and codelivery of a CpG ODN in alginate coated chitosan nanoparticles. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 69 (2), 405–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2008.01.019>.
- Borges, O., Tavares, J., de Sousa, A., Borchard, G., Junginger, H.E., Cordeiro-da-Silva, A., 2007. Evaluation of the immune response following a short oral vaccination schedule with hepatitis B antigen encapsulated into alginate-coated chitosan nanoparticles. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 32 (4), 278–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2007.08.005>.
- Borodkin, S. (2023). Ion-exchange resin delivery systems. In *Polymers for Controlled Drug Delivery* (pp. 215–230). CRC Press.
- Bose, A., Elyagoby, A., Wong, T.W., 2014. Oral 5-fluorouracil colon-specific delivery through in vivo pellet coating for colon cancer and aberrant crypt foci treatment. *Int. J. Pharm.* 468 (1), 178–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2014.04.006>.
- Burkersroda, F.v., Schedl, L., Göpferich, A., 2002. Why degradable polymers undergo surface erosion or bulk erosion. *Biomaterials* 23 (21), 4221–4231. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612\(02\)00170-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612(02)00170-9).
- Business, A. (2026). Polypropylene price index <https://businessanalytiq.com/procurementanalytics/index/polypropylene-price-index/>.

- Buzgo, M., Mickova, A., Rampichova, M., Doupnik, M., 2018. Blend electrospinning, coaxial electrospinning, and emulsion electrospinning techniques. In: Focarete, M.L., Tampieri, A. (Eds.), *Core-Shell Nanostructures for Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 11. Woodhead Publishing, pp. 325–347.
- Castañeda-Reyes, E.D., Perea-Flores, M.J., Davila-Ortiz, G., Lee, Y., Gonzalez de Mejia, E., 2020. Development, Characterization and use of Liposomes as Amphipathic Transporters of Bioactive Compounds for Melanoma Treatment and Reduction of Skin Inflammation: a Review. *Int. J. Nanomed.* 15, 7627–7650. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijn.S263516>.
- Catalin Balaura, P., & Mihai Grumesciu, A. J. C. T. i. M. C. (2015). Smart synthetic polymer nanocarriers for controlled and site-specific drug delivery. 15(15), 1424–1490.
- Cerqueira-Coutinho, C., Santos-Oliveira, R., dos Santos, E., & Mansur, C. R. (2015). Development of a photoprotective and antioxidant nanoemulsion containing chitosan as an agent for improving skin retention. 15(6), 593–604. doi: 10.1002/elsc.201400154.
- Chandel, V., Biswas, D., Roy, S., Vaidya, D., Verma, A., Gupta, A., 2022. Current Advances in Pectin: Extraction, Properties and Multifunctional Applications. *Foods* 11 (17). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11172683>.
- Chen, T. e., Tu, L., Wang, G., Qi, N., Wu, W., Zhang, W., & Feng, J. (2020). Multi-functional chitosan polymeric micelles as oral paclitaxel delivery systems for enhanced bioavailability and anti-tumor efficacy. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 578, 119105. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2020.119105.
- Ciolacu, D.E., Nicu, R., Ciolacu, F., 2020. Cellulose-based Hydrogels as Sustained Drug-delivery Systems. *Materials* 13 (22), 5270. <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1944/13/22/5270>.
- de la Rica, R., Aili, D., Stevens, M.M., 2012. Enzyme-responsive nanoparticles for drug release and diagnostics. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 64 (11), 967–978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2012.01.002>.
- Delahousse, J., Skarbek, C., Paci, A., 2019. Prodrugs as drug delivery system in oncology. *Cancer Chemother. Pharmacol.* 84 (5), 937–958. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00280-019-03906-2>.
- Desai, N., Rana, D., Salave, S., Gupta, R., Patel, P., Karunakaran, B., Sharma, A., Giri, J., Benival, D., Kommineni, N., 2023. Chitosan: a potential Biopolymer in Drug delivery and Biomedical applications. *Pharmaceutics* 15 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15041313>.
- Deshmukh, K., Kovářik, T., Kronek, T., Docheva, D., Stich, T., Pola, J., 2020. Recent advances and future perspectives of sol–gel derived porous bioactive glasses: a review [10.1039/D0RA04287K]. *RSC Adv.* 10 (56), 33782–33835. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0RA04287K>.
- Deveci, E., 2025. Nanoemulsions in cosmetics: Enhancing efficacy and stability. *Journal of Dermatologic Science and Cosmetic Technology* 2 (3), 100107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdsct.2025.100107>.
- Dunne, M., Regenold, M., Allen, C., 2020. Hyperthermia can alter tumor physiology and improve chemo- and radio-therapy efficacy. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 163–164, 98–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2020.07.007>.
- Elzoghby, A.O., Abo El-Fotoh, W.S., Elgindy, N.A., 2011. Casein-based formulations as promising controlled release drug delivery systems. *J. Control. Release* 153 (3), 206–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2011.02.010>.
- Ezhilarasi, P.N., Karthik, P., Chhanwal, N., Anandharamkrishnan, C., 2013. Nanoencapsulation Techniques for Food Bioactive Components: a Review. *Food Bioproc. Tech.* 6 (3), 628–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-012-0944-0>.
- Ezike, T.C., Okpara, U.S., Onoja, U.L., Nwike, C.P., Ezeako, E.C., Okpara, O.J., Okoroafor, C.C., Eze, S.C., Kalu, O.L., Odoh, E.C., Nwadike, U.G., Ogbodo, J.O., Umeh, B.U., Ossai, E.C., Nwanguma, B.C., 2023. Advances in drug delivery systems, challenges and future directions. *Heliyon* 9 (6), e17488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17488>.
- Fan, L.-F., He, W., Bai, M., Du, Q., Xiang, B., Chang, Y.-Z., Cao, D.-Y., 2008. Biphasic Drug Release: Permeability and Swelling of Pectin/Ethylcellulose Films, and *in Vitro* and *in Vivo* Correlation of Film-Coated Pellets in dogs. *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* 56 (8), 1118–1125. <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.56.1118>.
- Fathi, M., Ranjbari, F., Joudi, M., Farazmand, P., Iranijam, E., Haghi-Aminjan, H., Fathi, F., 2025. Preparation of Silk Fibroin Nanofibers Containing 5-Fluorouracil for pH-sensitive Drug delivery and Synergistic Cancer Therapy. *BioNanoScience* 15 (2), 250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12668-025-01857-y>.
- Ferraro, C., Dattilo, M., Patitucci, F., Prete, S., Scopelliti, G., Parisi, O.I., Puoci, F., 2024. Exploring Protein-based Carriers in Drug delivery. A Review. *Pharmaceutics* 16 (9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics16091172>.
- Ferreira, L.M.B., Zucolotto, V., 2024. Chitosan-based nanomedicines: a review of the main challenges for translating the science of polyelectrolyte complexation into innovative pharmaceutical products. *Carbohydr. Polym. Technol. Appl.* 7, 100441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carpta.2024.100441>.
- Fink, C., Sun, D., Wagner, K., Schneider, M., Bauer, H., Dolgos, H., Mäder, K., Peters, S. A., 2020. Evaluating the Role of Solubility in Oral Absorption of Poorly Water-Soluble Drugs using Physiologically-based Pharmacokinetic Modeling. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.* 107 (3), 650–661. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.1672>.
- Fu, S.-Y., Feng, X.-Q., Lauke, B., Mai, Y.-W., 2008. Effects of particle size, particle/matrix interface adhesion and particle loading on mechanical properties of particulate–polymer composites. *Compos. B Eng.* 39 (6), 933–961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2008.01.002>.
- Fu, Y., Kao, W.J., 2010. Drug release kinetics and transport mechanisms of non-degradable and degradable polymeric delivery systems. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 7 (4), 429–444. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425241003602259>.
- Gandhi, S., Roy, I., 2019. Doxorubicin-loaded casein nanoparticles for drug delivery: Preparation, characterization and *in vitro* evaluation. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 121, 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.10.005>.
- Garg, T., Arora, S., Pahwa, R., 2025. Cellulose and its derivatives: Structure, modification, and application in controlled drug delivery. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 11 (1), 76. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-025-00834-2>.
- Ghosh, S., Singh, B.P., Webster, T.J., 2021. Chapter 14 - Nanoparticle-impregnated biopolymers as novel antimicrobial nanofilms. In: Rai, M., dos Santos, C.A. (Eds.), *Biopolymer-Based Nano Films*. Elsevier, pp. 269–309.
- Gu, H., Chen, P., Liu, X., Lian, Y., Xi, J., Li, J., Song, J., Li, X., 2023. Trimethylated chitosan-coated flexible liposomes with resveratrol for topical drug delivery to reduce blue-light-induced retinal damage. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 252, 126480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.126480>.
- Guo, X., Chang, R.-K., & Hussain, M. A. J. J. o. p. s. (2009). Ion-exchange resins as drug delivery carriers. 98(11), 3886–3902.
- Hamedinasab, H., Rezaian, A.H., Mellat, M., Mashreghi, M., Jaafari, M.R., 2020. Development of chitosan-coated liposome for pulmonary delivery of N-acetylcysteine. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 156, 1455–1463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.11.190>.
- Hao, M., Tan, X., Liu, K., Xin, N., 2025. Nanoencapsulation of nutraceuticals: enhancing stability and bioavailability in functional foods. *Front. Nutr.* 12, 1746176. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2025.1746176>.
- Hartman, C., Popowski, Y., Raichman, D., Amir, E. J. J. o. C. T., & Research. (2020). Biodegradable polymer coating for controlled release of hydrophobic functional molecules from cotton fabrics. 17, 669–679.
- Hasan, N., Rahman, L., Kim, S.-H., Cao, J., Arjuna, A., Lallo, S., Jhun, B.H., Yoo, J.-W., 2020. Recent advances of nanocellulose in drug delivery systems. *J. Pharm. Investig.* 50 (6), 553–572. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40005-020-00499-4>.
- Hasanbegloo, K., Banihashem, S., Faraji Dizaji, B., Bybordi, S., Farrokhi-Eslamlou, N., Abadi, P.G., Jazi, F.S., Irani, M., 2023. Paclitaxel-loaded liposome-incorporated chitosan (core)/poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/chitosan (shell) nanofibers for the treatment of breast cancer. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 230, 123380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123380>.
- He, W., Du, Q., Cao, D.-Y., Xiang, B., Fan, L.-F., 2008. Study on colon-specific pectin/ethylcellulose film-coated 5-fluorouracil pellets in rats. *Int. J. Pharm.* 348 (1), 35–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2007.07.005>.
- Heredia, N.S., Vizuete, K., Flores-Calero, M., Pazmiño, V.K., Pilaquina, F., Kumar, B., Debut, A., 2022. Comparative statistical analysis of the release kinetics models for nanoprecipitated drug delivery systems based on poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid). *PLoS One* 17 (3), e0264825. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0264825>.
- Homaigohar, S., & Boccacini, A. R. (2022). Nature-Derived and Synthetic Additives to poly(ϵ -Caprolactone) Nanofibrous Systems for Biomedicine; an Updated Overview [Review]. 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2021.809676>.
- Honda-Okubo, Y., Saade, F., Petrovsky, N., 2012. Advax™, a polysaccharide adjuvant derived from delta inulin, provides improved influenza vaccine protection through broad-based enhancement of adaptive immune responses. *Vaccine* 30 (36), 5373–5381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2012.06.021>.
- Hong, S., Choi, D.W., Kim, H.N., Park, C.G., Lee, W., Park, H.H., 2020. Protein-based Nanoparticles as Drug delivery Systems. *Pharmaceutics* 12 (7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12070604>.
- Huang, G., Liu, Y., Chen, L., 2017. Chitosan and its derivatives as vehicles for drug delivery. *Drug Deliv.* 24 (sup1), 108–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10717544.2017.1399305>.
- Hynes, C.G., Morra, E., Walsh, P., Buchanan, F., 2023. Chapter 7 - Degradation of biomaterials. In: De Boer, J., Blitterswijk, C.A.V., Uquillas, J.A., Malik, N. (Eds.), *Tissue Engineering, Third Edition*. Academic Press, pp. 213–259.
- Idrees, H., Zaidi, S. Z. J., Sabir, A., Khan, R. U., Zhang, X., & Hassan, S.-u. (2020). A Review of Biodegradable Natural Polymer-Based Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery Applications. 10(10), 1970. <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-4991/10/10/1970>.
- Inaji, H., Koyama, H., Higashiyama, M., Noguchi, S., Yamamoto, H., Ishikawa, O., Omichi, K., Iwanaga, T., Wada, A., 1991. Immunohistochemical, ultrastructural and biochemical studies of an amylase-producing breast carcinoma. *Virchows Arch. A Pathol. Anat. Histopathol.* 419 (1), 29–33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01600149>.
- Jain, R., Shetty, S., Yadav, K.S., 2020. Unfolding the electrospinning potential of biopolymers for preparation of nanofibers. *J. Drug Delivery Sci. Technol.* 57, 101604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2020.101604>.
- Jem, K.J., Tan, B., 2020. The development and challenges of poly (lactic acid) and poly (glycolic acid). *Adv. Ind. Eng. Polym. Res.* 3 (2), 60–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiepr.2020.01.002>.
- Kamaly, N., Yameen, B., Wu, J., Farokhzad, O.C., 2016. Degradable Controlled-Release Polymers and Polymeric Nanoparticles: Mechanisms of Controlling Drug Release. *Chem. Rev.* 116 (4), 2602–2663. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00346>.
- Kapoor, D.U., Garg, R., Gaur, M., Pareek, A., Prajapati, B.G., Castro, G.R., Suttirungwong, S., Sriamornsak, P., 2024. Pectin hydrogels for controlled drug release: recent developments and future prospects. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal* 32 (4), 102002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2024.102002>.
- Khalbas, A.H., Albayati, T.M., Ali, N.S., Salih, I.K., 2024. Drug loading methods and kinetic release models using of mesoporous silica nanoparticles as a drug delivery system: a review. *S. Afr. J. Chem. Eng.* 50, 261–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajce.2024.08.013>.
- Khaleel Basha, S., Syed Muzammil, M., Dhandayuthabani, R., Sugantha Kumari, V., 2021. Development of nanoemulsion of Alginate/*Aloe vera* for oral delivery of insulin. *Mater. Today Proc.* 36, 357–363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.04.138>.
- Khotimchenko, M., 2020. Pectin polymers for colon-targeted antitumor drug delivery. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.05.002>.
- Kim, T.H., Jiang, H.H., Youn, Y.S., Park, C.W., Tak, K.K., Lee, S., Kim, H., Jon, S., Chen, X., Lee, K.C., 2011. Preparation and characterization of water-soluble

- albumin-bound curcumin nanoparticles with improved antitumor activity. *Int. J. Pharm.* 403 (1), 285–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2010.10.041>.
- Klara, J., Hinz, A., Bzowska, M., Horak, W., Lewandowska-Lańcucka, J., 2024. In vitro/ex vivo evaluation of multifunctional collagen/chitosan/hyaluronic acid hydrogel-based alendronate delivery systems. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 262, 130142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.130142>.
- Komaiko, J., Sastrosubroto, A., McClements, D.J., 2016. Encapsulation of ω -3 fatty acids in nanoemulsion-based delivery systems fabricated from natural emulsifiers: Sunflower phospholipids. *Food Chem.* 203, 331–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.02.080>.
- Kong, M., Yang, H., Fan, D., Deng, J., 2026. pH-responsive Sodium Alginate Micro-Nano Hydrogels for Oral Insulin delivery: Enhancing Therapeutic Efficacy and reducing Hypoglycemic Risk. *Food Front.* 7 (2), e70187. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fft2.70187>.
- Lan, Y., Ohm, J.-B., Chen, B., Rao, J., 2021. Microencapsulation of hemp seed oil by pea protein isolate–sugar beet pectin complex coacervation: Influence of coacervation pH and wall/core ratio. *Food Hydrocoll.* 113, 106423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.106423>.
- Lautenschläger, C., Schmidt, C., Fischer, D., Stallmach, A., 2014. Drug delivery strategies in the therapy of inflammatory bowel disease. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 71, 58–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2013.10.001>.
- Li, S., Wang, Q., Jia, Z., Da, M., Zhao, J., Yang, R., Chen, D., 2023. Recent advances in glucose oxidase-based nanocarriers for tumor targeting therapy. *Heliyon* 9 (10), e20407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20407>.
- Li, X., Anton, N., Arpagaus, C., Belleiteix, F., Vandamme, T.F., 2010. Nanoparticles by spray drying using innovative new technology: the Büchi Nano Spray Dryer B-90. *J. Control. Release* 147 (2), 304–310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2010.07.113>.
- Liang, Y., Luo, T., Li, F., Wang, J., Tang, Y., 2025. Comparative study of injectable and stimuli-responsive hydrogels reinforced with cellulose nanofibers and chitosan for controlled drug delivery. *Chem. Eng. J.* 525, 170381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.170381>.
- Liao, J., Huang, H., 2020. Review on magnetic Natural Polymer Constructed Hydrogels as Vehicles for Drug delivery. *Biomacromolecules* 21 (7), 2574–2594. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.0c00566>.
- Liberti, M.V., Locasale, J.W., 2016. The Warburg effect: how does it Benefit Cancer Cells? *Trends Biochem. Sci.* 41 (3), 211–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibs.2015.12.001>.
- Liu, L., Yao, W., Rao, Y., Lu, X., Gao, J., 2017. pH-responsive carriers for oral drug delivery: challenges and opportunities of current platforms. *Drug Deliv.* 24 (1), 569–581. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10717544.2017.1279238>.
- Liu, T.-Y., Chan, T.-Y., Wang, K.-S., Tsou, H.-M., 2015. Influence of magnetic nanoparticle arrangement in ferrogels for tunable biomolecule diffusion [10.1039/C5RA17306J]. *RSC Adv.* 5 (109), 90098–90102. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA17306J>.
- Liu, T.-Y., Hu, S.-H., Liu, K.-H., Liu, D.-M., Chen, S.-Y., 2006. Preparation and characterization of smart magnetic hydrogels and its use for drug release. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 304 (1), e397–e399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2006.01.203>.
- Luciano, B. (2022). Polyhydroxyalkanoates based systems: The future of drug delivery and tissue engineering devices. In *Bio-Based Nanomaterials* (pp. 133–169). Elsevier.
- Luraghi, A., Peri, F., Moroni, L., 2021. Electrospinning for drug delivery applications: a review. *J. Control. Release* 334, 463–484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.03.033>.
- Mall, J., Naseem, N., Haider, M.F., Rahman, M.A., Khan, S., Siddiqui, S.N., 2024. Nanostructured lipid carriers as a drug delivery system: a comprehensive review with therapeutic applications. *Intelligent Pharmacy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipha.2024.09.005>.
- Man, E., Lamprou, D., Easdon, C., McLellan, I., Yiu, H.H.P., Hoskins, C., 2022. Exploration of dual Ionic Cross-Linked Alginate Hydrogels Via Cations of Varying Valences towards Wound Healing. *Polymers* 14 (23), 5192. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4360/14/23/5192>.
- Meena, P., Singh, P., Warkar, S.G., 2025. Degradable pH-sensitive Calcium-Crosslinked Tragacanth Gum/ β -Cyclodextrin/Sodium Alginate Hydrogel Microspheres Prepared via Ionotropic Gelation Technique for Hydrophobic Drug delivery. *J. Polym. Environ.* 33 (2), 928–944. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-024-03449-5>.
- Méndez, D.A., Schroeter, B., Martínez-Abad, A., Fabra, M.J., Gurikov, P., López-Rubio, A., 2023. Pectin-based aerogel particles for drug delivery: effect of pectin composition on aerogel structure and release properties. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 306, 120604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.120604>.
- MH, G. D., & Marzuka, M. (2014). Lyophilized Chitosan/xanthan Polyelectrolyte Complex Based Mucoadhesive Inserts for Nasal Delivery of Promethazine Hydrochloride. *Iran J Pharm Res*, 13(3), 769–784.
- Mishra, R.K., Datt, M., Pal, K., Bantia, A.K., 2008. Preparation and characterization of amidated pectin based hydrogels for drug delivery system. *J. Mater. Sci. - Mater. Med.* 19 (6), 2275–2280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-007-3310-4>.
- Mohsin, M.E.A., Siddiqi, A.J., Mousa, S., Shrivastava, N.K., 2025. Design, Characterization, and Release Kinetics of a Hybrid Hydrogel Drug delivery System for Sustained Hormone Therapy. *Polymers* 17 (8), 999. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4360/17/8/999>.
- Motsone, F., Abrahamse, H., Dhilip Kumar, S.S., 2023. Multifunctional lipid-based nanoparticles for wound healing and antibacterial applications: a review. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* 321, 103002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2023.103002>.
- Mousavi, S.J., Heydari, P., Javaherchi, P., Kharazi, A.Z., Zarrabi, A., 2025. Alginate-based nanocomposite incorporating chitosan nanoparticles: a dual-drug delivery system for infection control and wound regeneration. *J. Drug Delivery Sci. Technol.* 107, 106755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2025.106755>.
- Mtibe, A., Motloung, M.P., Bandyopadhyay, J., Ray, S.S., 2021. Synthetic Biopolymers and their Composites: Advantages and Limitations—An Overview. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 42 (15), 2100130. <https://doi.org/10.1002/marc.202100130>.
- Mumtaz Virk, M., Reimhult, E., 2018. Phospholipase A2-Induced Degradation and Release from Lipid-Containing Polymersomes. *Langmuir* 34 (1), 395–405. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.7b03893>.
- Mura, P., Maestrelli, F., Cirri, M., Mennini, N., 2022. Multiple Roles of Chitosan in Mucosal Drug delivery: an Updated Review. *Mar. Drugs* 20 (5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/md20050335>.
- Murueva, A.V., Shershneva, A.M., Shishatskaya, E.I., Volova, T.G., 2023. Characteristics of Microparticles based on Resorbable Polyhydroxyalkanoates Loaded with Antibacterial and Cytostatic. *Drugs* 24 (19), 14983. <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/24/19/14983>.
- Nait Mohamed, F.A., Laraba-Djebbari, F., 2016. Development and characterization of a new carrier for vaccine delivery based on calcium-alginate nanoparticles: Safe immunoprotective approach against scorpion envenoming. *Vaccine* 34 (24), 2692–2699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2016.04.035>.
- Nasrollahzadeh, M., Sajjadi, M., Nezafat, Z., & Shafiei, N. (2021). Chapter 3 - Polysaccharide biopolymer chemistry. In M. Nasrollahzadeh (Ed.), *Biopolymer-Based Metal Nanoparticle Chemistry for Sustainable Applications* (pp. 45–105). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-822108-2.00019-3>.
- Nezamdoost-Sani, N., Amiri, S., Mousavi Khaneghah, A., 2024. The application of the coacervation technique for microencapsulation bioactive ingredients: a critical review. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research* 18, 101431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2024.101431>.
- Nisini, R., Poerio, N., Mariotti, S., De Santis, F., Fraziano, M., 2018. The Multirole of Liposomes in Therapy and Prevention of. *Infect. Dis. [Review]* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2018.00155>.
- Nsairat, H., Khater, D., Sayed, U., Odeh, F., Al Bawab, A., Alshaer, W., 2022. Liposomes: structure, composition, types, and clinical applications. *Heliyon* 8 (5), e09394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09394>.
- Nwagwu, C., Onugwu, A., Echezona, A., Uzundu, S., Agbo, C., Kenchukwu, F., Ogbonna, J., Ugorji, L., Nwobi, L., Nwobi, O., Mmuotuo, O., Ezeibe, E., Loretz, B., Tarirai, C., Mbara, K.C., Agumah, N., Nnamani, P., Ofokansi, K., Lehr, C.-M., Attama, A., 2024. Biopolymeric and lipid-based nanotechnological strategies for the design and development of novel mosquito repellent systems: recent advances. *Nanoscale Adv.* 6 (19), 4751–4780. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4na00474d>.
- Oshi, M.A., Lee, J., Kim, J., Hasan, N., Im, E., Jung, Y., Yoo, J.-W., 2021. pH-responsive Alginate-based Microparticles for Colon-Targeted delivery of Pure Cyclosporine A Crystals to Treat Ulcerative Colitis. *Pharmaceutics* 13 (9), 1412. <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4923/13/9/1412>.
- Osmalek, T., Milanowski, B., Froelich, A., Szybowicz, M., Białowas, W., Kapela, M., Gadziński, P., Ancukiewicz, K., 2017. Design and characteristics of gellan gum beads for modified release of meloxicam. *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.* 43 (8), 1314–1329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03639045.2017.1318896>.
- Owens, G.J., Singh, R.K., Foroutan, F., Alqaysi, M., Han, C.-M., Mahapatra, C., Kim, H.-W., Knowles, J.C., 2016. Sol-gel based materials for biomedical applications. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 77, 1–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2015.12.001>.
- Padekan, B., Dadvand Koohi, A., Akbari Dogolsar, M., 2025. Collagen-based Hydrogel with Incorporated Nano-Hydroxyapatite for the delivery of a Poorly Water-Soluble Drug. *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part B* 64 (10), 1250–1269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222348.2024.2389663>.
- Palanikumar, L., Al-Hosani, S., Kalmouni, M., Nguyen, V. P., Ali, L., Pasricha, R., Barrera, F. N., & Magzoub, M. J. C. b. (2020). pH-responsive high stability polymeric nanoparticles for targeted delivery of anticancer therapeutics. 3(1), 95.
- Pani, N.R., Nath, L.K., 2014. Development of controlled release tablet by optimizing HPMC: Consideration of theoretical release and RSM. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 104, 238–245.
- Park, H., Otte, A., Park, K., 2022. Evolution of drug delivery systems: from 1950 to 2020 and beyond. *J. Control. Release* 342, 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.12.030>.
- Pawar, R., Pathan, A., Nagaraj, S., Kapare, H., Giram, P., & Wavhale, R. J. P. f. a. t. (2023). Polycaprolactone and its derivatives for drug delivery. 34(10), 3296–3316.
- Pirotta, V., Bisbano, G., Serra, M., Torre, M. L., Doria, F., Bari, E., & Paolillo, M. (2023). cRGD-Functionalized Silk Fibroin Nanoparticles: A Strategy for Cancer Treatment with a Potent Unselective Naphthalene Diimide Derivative. *Cancers (Basel)*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers15061725>.
- Prakash, P., Lee, W.-H., Loo, C.-Y., Wong, H. S. J., & Parumasivam, T. J. N. (2022). Advances in polyhydroxyalkanoate nanocarriers for effective drug delivery: An overview and challenges. 12(1), 175.
- Puiggali-Jou, A., del Valle, L.J., Alemán, C., 2019. Drug delivery systems based on intrinsically conducting polymers. *J. Control. Release* 309, 244–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2019.07.035>.
- Rautio, J., Meanwell, N.A., Di, L., Hageman, M.J., 2018. The expanding role of prodrugs in contemporary drug design and development. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 17 (8), 559–587. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd.2018.46>.
- Reddy, M.S.B., Ponnamma, D., Choudhary, R., Sadasivuni, K.K., 2021. A Comparative Review of Natural and Synthetic Biopolymer Composite Scaffolds. *Polymers* 13 (7), 1105. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4360/13/7/1105>.
- Rezagholidze-shirvan, A., Soltani, M., Shokri, S., Radfar, R., Arab, M., Shamloo, E., 2024. Bioactive compound encapsulation: Characteristics, applications in food systems, and implications for human health. *Food Chem.: X* 24, 101953. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochx.2024.101953>.
- Robles, E., Juárez, J., Burboa, M. G., Gutiérrez, L. E., Taboada, P., Mosquera, V., & Valdez, M. A. J. J. o. A. P. S. (2014). Properties of insulin–chitosan complexes obtained by an alkylation reaction on chitosan. 131(6).

- Said, N.S., Olawuyi, I.F., Lee, W.Y., 2023. Pectin Hydrogels: Gel-Forming Behaviors. Mechanisms, and Food Applications. *Gels* 9 (9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels9090732>.
- Sajeev, D., Rajesh, A., Nethish Kumar, R., Aswin, D., Jayakumar, R., Nair, S.C., 2025. Chemically modified chitosan as a functional biomaterial for drug delivery system. *Carbohydr. Res.* 548, 109351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carres.2024.109351>.
- Samec, T., Boulos, J., Gilmore, S., Hazelton, A., Alexander-Bryant, A., 2022. Peptide-based delivery of therapeutics in cancer treatment. *Mater. Today Bio* 14, 100248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2022.100248>.
- Samia, O., Hanan, R., Kamal, E.T., 2012. Carbamazepine mucoadhesive nanoemulgel (MNEG) as brain targeting delivery system via the olfactory mucosa. *Drug Deliv.* 19 (1), 58–67.
- Sampath U. Gunathilake, T. M., Ching, Y. C., Chuah, C. H., Rahman, N. A., & Nai-Shang, L. (2020). pH-responsive poly(lactic acid)/sodium carboxymethyl cellulose film for enhanced delivery of curcumin in vitro. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 58, 101787. doi: 10.1016/j.jddst.2020.101787.
- Schmaljohann, D., 2006. Thermo- and pH-responsive polymers in drug delivery. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 58 (15), 1655–1670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2006.09.020>.
- Scomparin, A., Florindo, H.F., Tiram, G., Ferguson, E.L., Satchi-Fainaro, R., 2017. Two-step polymer- and liposome-enzyme prodrug therapies for cancer: PDEPT and PELT concepts and future perspectives. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 118, 52–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2017.09.011>.
- Serrano, D.R., Luciano, F.C., Anaya, B.J., Ongoren, B., Kara, A., Molina, G., Ramirez, B.I., Sánchez-Guirales, S.A., Simon, J.A., Tomietto, G., Rapti, C., Ruiz, H.K., Rawat, S., Kumar, D., Lalatsa, A., 2024. Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in Drug Discovery and Drug delivery. Revolutionizing Personalized Medicine. *Pharmaceutics* 16 (10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics16101328>.
- Sezer, A. D., Bucak, S., & Çağdaş, M. (2014). Liposomes as Potential Drug Carrier Systems for Drug Delivery. In A. D. Sezer (Ed.), *Application of Nanotechnology in Drug Delivery*. IntechOpen. doi: 10.5772/58459.
- Shaikh, M. A. J., Gupta, G., Afzal, O., Gupta, M. M., Goyal, A., Altamimi, A. S. A., Alzarea, S. I., Almalki, W. H., Kazmi, I., & Negi, P. J. I. j. o. b. m. (2023). Sodium alginate-based drug delivery for diabetes management: A review. 236, 123986.
- Shiledar, R.R., Tagalpallewar, A.A., Kokare, C.R., 2014. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of xanthan gum-based bilayered mucoadhesive buccal patches of zolmitriptan. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 101, 1234–1242.
- Shin, H.C., Alani, A.W., Rao, D.A., Rockich, N.C., Kwon, G.S., 2009. Multi-drug loaded polymeric micelles for simultaneous delivery of poorly soluble anticancer drugs. *J. Control. Release* 140 (3), 294–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2009.04.024>.
- Shokri, J., & Adibkia, K. (2013). Application of cellulose and cellulose derivatives in pharmaceutical industries. In *Cellulose-medical, pharmaceutical and electronic applications*. IntechOpen.
- Siepmann, J., Siepmann, F., 2011. Swelling controlled drug delivery systems. In: *Fundamentals and Applications of Controlled Release Drug Delivery*. Springer, pp. 153–170.
- Siles-Sánchez, M. d. I. N., García-Ponsoda, P., Fernandez-Jalao, I., Jaime, L., & Santoyo, S. (2024). Development of Pectin Particles as a Colon-Targeted Marjoram Phenolic Compound Delivery System. *Foods*, 13(2), 188. <https://www.mdpi.com/2304-8158/13/2/188>.
- Sill, T.J., von Recum, H.A., 2008. Electrospinning: applications in drug delivery and tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* 29 (13), 1989–2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2008.01.011>.
- Silva, R.R.A., Marques, C.S., Arruda, T.R., Teixeira, S.C., de Oliveira, T.V., 2023. Biodegradation of Polymers: Stages, Measurement, Standards and Prospects. 3 (2), 371–399. <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-6209/3/2/23>.
- Singh, Y., Palombo, M., Sinko, P.J., 2008. Recent trends in targeted anticancer prodrug and conjugate design. *Curr. Med. Chem.* 15 (18), 1802–1826. <https://doi.org/10.2174/092986708785132997>.
- Sriamornsak, P., & Nunthanid, J. (1998). Calcium pectinate gel beads for controlled release drug delivery: I. Preparation and in vitro release studies. Paper presented in part at the Eleventh International Symposium on Microencapsulation held at Bangkok, Thailand, 27–29 August 1997. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 160(2), 207–212. doi: 10.1016/S0378-5173(97)00310-4.
- Srikanth, M., Sunil, S., Rao, N., Uhumwangho, M., & Murthy, K. R. J. J. o. S. R. (2010). Ion-exchange resins as controlled drug delivery carriers. 2(3), 597–597.
- Srivastava, A., Bhati, P., Singh, S., Agrawal, M., Kumari, N., Vashisth, P., Chauhan, P., & Bhatnagar, N. (2024). A review on polylactic acid-based blends/composites and the role of compatibilizers in biomedical engineering applications. 64(3), 1003–1044. doi: 10.1002/pen.26626.
- Stevenson, C.L., Santini Jr., J.T., Langer, R., 2012. Reservoir-based drug delivery systems utilizing microtechnology. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 64 (14), 1590–1602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2012.02.005>.
- Sun, R., Chen, Y., Pei, Y., Wang, W., Zhu, Z., Zheng, Z., Yang, L., Sun, L., 2024. The drug release of PLGA-based nanoparticles and their application in treatment of gastrointestinal cancers. *Heliyon* 10 (18), e38165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e38165>.
- Syed Mohamed, S. M. D., Ansari, N. F., Md Iqbal, N., Anis, S. N. S. J. I. J. o. P. M., & Biomaterials, P. (2022). Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA)-based responsive polymers. 71(17), 1283–1302.
- Ta, T., Porter, T.M., 2013. Thermosensitive liposomes for localized delivery and triggered release of chemotherapy. *J. Control. Release* 169 (1–2), 112–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2013.03.036>.
- Unagolla, J.M., Jayasuriya, A.C., 2018. Drug transport mechanisms and in vitro release kinetics of vancomycin encapsulated chitosan-alginate polyelectrolyte microparticles as a controlled drug delivery system. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 114, 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2017.12.012>.
- Urbaniak, T., Milasheuski, Y., Musiał, W., 2024. Zero-Order Kinetics Release of Lamivudine from Layer-by-Layer Coated Macromolecular Prodrug Particles. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 25 (23), 12921. <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/25/23/12921>.
- Varma, M.V.S., Kaushal, A.M., Garg, A., Garg, S., 2004. Factors affecting mechanism and kinetics of drug release from matrix-based oral controlled drug delivery systems. *Am. J. Drug Deliv.* 2 (1), 43–57. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00137696-200402010-00003>.
- Venkatesh, D.N., Meyyanathan, S.N., Kovacevic, A., Zielińska, A., Fonseca, J., Eder, P., Dobrowolska, A., Souto, E.B., 2022. Effect of Hydrophilic Polymers on the Release Rate and Pharmacokinetics of Acyclovir Tablets Obtained by Wet Granulation: In Vitro and In Vivo Assays. *Molecules* 27 (19), 6490. <https://www.mdpi.com/1420-3049/27/19/6490>.
- Visan, A.I., Popescu-Pelin, G., Socol, G., 2021. Degradation Behavior of Polymers used as Coating Materials for Drug Delivery—A basic. *Review* 13 (8), 1272. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4360/13/8/1272>.
- Vlachopoulos, A., Karlioti, G., Balla, E., Daniilidis, V., Kalamas, T., Stefanidou, M., Bikiaris, N. D., Christodoulou, E., Koumentakou, I., & Karavas, E. J. P. (2022). Poly (lactic acid)-based microparticles for drug delivery applications: An overview of recent advances. 14(2), 359.
- Wang, B., Akanbi, T.O., Agyei, D., Holland, B.J., Barrow, C.J., 2018. Chapter 7 - Coacervation Technique as an Encapsulation and delivery Tool for Hydrophobic Biofunctional Compounds. In: Grumescescu, A.M., Holban, A.M. (Eds.), *Role of Materials Science in Food Bioengineering*. Academic Press, pp. 235–261.
- Wang, Q., Chen, W., Zhu, W., McClements, D., Xuebo, L., Liu, F., 2022. A review of multilayer and composite films and coatings for active biodegradable packaging. *npj Sci. Food* 6, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41538-022-00132-8>.
- Wang, Q.-W., Liu, X.-Y., Liu, L., Feng, J., Li, Y.-H., Guo, Z.-J., Mei, Q.-B., 2007. Synthesis and evaluation of the 5-fluorouracil-pectin conjugate targeted at the colon. *Med. Chem. Res.* 16 (7–9), 370–379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-007-9049-0>.
- Wang, S., Liu, R., Fu, Y., Kao, W.J., 2020. Release mechanisms and applications of drug delivery systems for extended-release. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 17 (9), 1289–1304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425247.2020.1788541>.
- Wang, S.-Y., Tohti, M., Zhang, J.-Q., Li, J., Li, D.-Q., 2023. Acylhydrazone-derived whole pectin-based hydrogel as an injectable drug delivery system. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 251, 126276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.126276>.
- Wang, Y., Shen, Z., Wang, H., Song, Z., Yu, D., Li, G., Liu, X., Liu, W., 2025. Progress in Research on Metal Ion Crosslinking Alginate-based Gels. *Gels* 11 (1), 16. <https://www.mdpi.com/2310-2861/11/1/16>.
- Ward, A., Brown, B., Walton, K., Timmins, P., Conway, B.R., Asare-Addo, K., 2020. Application of Focus Variation Microscopy and Dissolution Imaging in Understanding the Behaviour of Hydrophilic Matrices. *Pharmaceutics* 12 (12), 1162. <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4923/12/12/1162>.
- Wei, Y., Guo, A., Liu, Z., Mao, L., Yuan, F., Gao, Y., Mackie, A., 2021. Structural design of zein-cellulose nanocrystals core-shell microparticles for delivery of curcumin. *Food Chem.* 357, 129849. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.129849>.
- Yan, J., Chen, R., Zhang, H., Bryers, J.D., 2019. Injectable Biodegradable Chitosan-Alginate 3D Porous Gel Scaffold for mRNA Vaccine delivery. *Macromol. Biosci.* 19 (2), e1800242. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.201800242>.
- Yi, S., Zheng, J., Lv, P., Zhang, D., Zheng, X., Zhang, Y., Liao, R., 2018. Controlled Drug Release from Cyclodextrin-Gated Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles based on Switchable Host-Guest Interactions. *Bioconjug. Chem.* 29 (9), 2884–2891. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.8b00416>.
- Zargar, S. M., Hafshejani, D. K., Eskandarinia, A., Rafienia, M., Kharazi, A. Z. J. J. o. M. S., & Sensors. (2019). A review of controlled drug delivery systems based on cells and cell membranes. 9(3), 181–189.
- Zhang, D., Sun, P., Li, P., Xue, A., Zhang, X., Zhang, H., Jin, X., 2013. A magnetic chitosan hydrogel for sustained and prolonged delivery of bacillus Calmette-Guérin in the treatment of bladder cancer. *Biomaterials* 34 (38), 10258–10266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2013.09.027>.
- Zhang, H.W., Wang, L.Q., Xiang, Q.F., Zhong, Q., Chen, L.M., Xu, C.X., Xiang, X.H., Xu, B., Meng, F., Wan, Y.Q., Deng, D.Y., 2014. Specific lipase-responsive polymer-coated gadolinium nanoparticles for MR imaging of early acute pancreatitis. *Biomaterials* 35 (1), 356–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2013.09.046>.
- Zhao, K., Chen, G., Shi, X.-m., Gao, T.-t., Li, W., Zhao, Y., Zhang, F.-q., Wu, J., Cui, X., & Wang, Y.-F. J. P. o. (2012). Preparation and efficacy of a live newcastle disease virus vaccine encapsulated in chitosan nanoparticles. 7(12), e53314.
- Zhou, N., Liu, Y.D., Zhang, Y., Gu, T.W., Peng, L.H., 2023. Pharmacological Functions, Synthesis, and delivery Progress for Collagen as Biodrug and Biomaterial. *Pharmaceutics* 15 (5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15051443>.
- Zielińska, M., Zielińska, M., Wilczyńska, M., Rojewska, M., Voelkel, A., Sandomierski, M., 2025. Optimization of a mucoadhesion testing protocol using a vertical force measurement system for chitosan- and pectin-based lyophilized polymer matrices and enteric-coated capsules. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 323, 147145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.147145>.
- Zucker, D., Marcus, D., Barenholz, Y., & Goldblum, A. J. J. o. c. r. (2009). Liposome drugs' loading efficiency: a working model based on loading conditions and drug's physicochemical properties. 139(1), 73–80.